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USLUBIY VA RITMIK OMILLARNING XITOIY TILI SINONIMIYASIGA TA'SIRI

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TDIU Xalqaro munosabatlar fakulteti

talabasi: Qosimov Shoymardon

TDIU Xorijiy tillar kafedrası

o'qituvchisi: Khikmatov Dilshodjon

Annatatsiya: Uslubiyat tilshunoslik fanining bir bo'limi bo'lib, nutq jarayonida til hodisalarining maqsadga, sharoitga va muhitga mos ravishda foydalanish qonuniyatlari bilan tanishtiradi. Uslubiyatda uslublar, til vositalarining nutqda qo'llanish yo'llari, fonetik, lug'aviy, frazeologik va grammatik birliklarning qo'llanish xususiyatlari o'rganiladi.

Kalit So'zlar: Uslub, Xitoy tilidagi uslubiy so'zlar, rasmiy uslub, publisistik uslub

Nutqning o'ziga xos usuli mavjud bo'lib:

1. 会话式 [huìhuà shì] So'zlashuv uslubi
2. 科学作风[kēxué zuòfēng] Ilmiy uslub
3. 正式行政风格 [zhèngshì xíngzhèng fēnggé] Rasmiy-idoraviy uslub
4. 流行（新闻）风格[Liúxíng (xīnwén) fēnggé] Ommabop (publitsistik)

uslub

5. 艺术风格[yìshù fēnggé] Badiiy uslub¹ shular jumlasidandir.

Huddi shu singari xitoy tilida ham so'zlashuv uslublari mavjud bo'lib bu uslubiyat jarayonida sinonim so'zlarning mos o'rindoshini tanlab olish zarur. Adabiy tilning ijtimoiy hayotdagi ma'lum bir sohada qo'llanadigan ko'rinishi adabiy

¹ С.Хохлов, “БКРС” М- 2004. 405/406-ср

til uslubi deyiladi. Xitoy tilida bu 文学风格 [Wén xué fēng gé] adabiy uslub deb yuritiladi.

Mazkur bo‘limda biz ritmik sinonimiya hodisasini uslub jihatidan tanlashga ta’sir qiluvchi omillarni tahlil qilib chiqamiz.

1. 会话式 [huìhuà shì] So‘zlashuv uslubi

Keng qo‘llanadigan uslublardan biri so‘zlashuv uslubidir. Bu uslubda ko‘pincha adabiy til me’yorlariga rioya qilinadi. So‘zlashuv uslubidagi nutq ko‘pincha dialogik shaklda bo‘ladi. Ikki yoki undan ortiq shaxsning gapidan dan tuzilgan nutq dialogik nutq deyiladi. Xitoy tilida so‘zlashuv uslubida ritmik xossalar uncha katta ro‘l o‘ynamaydi. Kontekst orqaliy berilayotgan iyeroglifni tushunish boshqa uslublarga qaraganda qiyin emas. Chunki xitoy tilida ham o‘zbek tilida ham so‘zlashuv uslubida ko‘pincha turli uslubiy bo‘yoqli so‘zlar, grammatik vositalar, tovushlarning tushib qolishi, orttirilishi mumkin: 我去大学，你呢？ [Wǒ qù dàxué, nǐ ne] men universitetga boraman sizchi? kontekstda kelgani uchun 呢 iyeroglifi “chi” deb tarjima qilinmoqda. Agar kontekst siz kelsa “qayerda” deb tarjima qilinadi. Masalan 你的朋友呢 [nǐ de péngyǒu ne] sizni do‘stingiz qayerda.

So‘zlashuv uslubida gapdagi so‘zlar tartibi ancha erkin bo‘ladi. Ko‘proq sodda gaplar, to‘liqsiz gaplar, undalmali gaplardan foydalaniladi. Adabiy til me’yorlariga qat’iy amal qilingan so‘zlashuv uslubi adabiy so‘zlashuv uslubi, bunday xususiyatga ega bo‘lmagan so‘zlashuv uslubi esa oddiy so‘zlashuv uslubidir.

2. 科学作风 [kēxué zuòfēng] Ilmiy uslub

Xitoy tilida ham o‘zbek tilida ham fan-texnikaning turli tarmoqlariga doir ilmiy asarlar, darsliklar ilmiy uslubda yoziladi. Ilmiy uslub aniq ma’lumotlar asosida chiqarilgan ilmiy xulosalar (qoidalar, ta’riflar)ga boy bo‘lishi bilan boshqa uslublardan farq qiladi: 本文提供有关大气的信息。 [běnwén tíngōng yǒuguān dàqì de xìnxi] - Bu maqolada atmosfera haqida ma’lumot berilgan. 大气层 [dà qì ceng] atmosfera - degan manoni anglatsada yuqoridagi kontekstda 大气 so‘zining o‘zi

olinmoqda chunkiy ilmiy uslubda gapda ritmni saqlash uchun 层 iyeroglifi tushurib qoldiriladi.

Ilmiy uslubda har bir fanning o‘ziga xos ilmiy atamalaridan foydalaniladi, bu uslubda so‘zlar o‘z ma'nosida qo‘llanadi, qoida yoki ta'rifning mazmunini ochishga xizmat qiladigan ajratilgan bo‘laklar, kirish so‘zlar, kirish birikmalar, shuningdek, qo‘shma gaplardan ko‘proq foydalaniladi.

3. 正式行政风格 [zhèngshì xíngzhèng fēnggé] Rasmiy-idoraviy uslub Hozirgi davrda rasmiy uslubning rivojlanishi Xitoyda islohotlar va ochiqlik siyosatini boshlanishi bilan bog‘liq. Pekin universiteti tilshunoslik manbalarini o‘rganish, undan tashqari, Gorelov V.I ning “Стилистика современного китайского языка“ kitobida stilistik leksikologiya, stilistik sintaksis va funksional uslublar tizimi² , grammatik tuzilishdagi faktlar hodisalarni tizimli tavsiflash va ilmiy yoritishga, rasmiy nutqning stilistik belgilari darajasini miqdoriy jihatdan baholashga undan tashqari leksik va sintaktik darajadagi rasmiy nutqning stilistik xususiyatlarini tahlil qilishga imkon beradi. Rasmiy uslub bu ish yuritish hujjatlari ichida eng muhim toifa bo‘lib, ish yuritish hujjatlariga ijtimoiy va xizmat maqsadlariga yo‘naltirilgan hujjatlar kiradi. Mazkur uslub davlat hayotidagi eng muhim bo‘g‘inlardan biri hisoblanadi. Ular bir davlatning davlat boshqaruvi, turli ijtimoiy ishlarni tartibga solishda qo‘llaniladigan kitobiy yozma quroldir. XXRda rasmiy hujjatlar partiya va davlat idoralarida boshqaruvchi partiya faoliyati va davlat boshqaruvi sohasida ularning xohish-irodasini ifodalash, biron mansab-martabaga tayinlash haqidagi farmonlarnin tarqatish maqsadlarida ishlatiladigan yozma qurol va vositadir. Partiya davlat idoralari sohasida rasmiy hujjatlar “partiya davlat idoralarini hayotga tatbiq etishni boshqarish, ijtimoiy faoliyatni tartibga solishdagi belgilangan samara va standart namunaga ega bo‘lgan ish yuritish uslubi va yozishmalar bo‘lib, partiya yo‘li, boshqarish tamoyillari, siyosati, ko‘rsatmalari,

² Горелов В.И. “Стилистика современного китайского языка“М.,“ Просвещения”-1979

joylashtiruv va kelishuv ishlarini to‘lalgicha amaliyotga tatbiq etishni tarqatish, savol so‘rash va ularga javob berish, biron vaziyat haqida hisobot berish va almashinish vositasidir”, davlat ma‘muriy idoralari sohasida rasmiy hujjatlar “ma‘muriy davlat idoralarining ma‘muriy boshqaruv jarayonida shakllangan qonun bilan belgilangan natija va standart shaklga ega bo‘lgan ish yuritish uslubi va yozishmalar bo‘lib, ijtimoiy faoliyatni qonunga muvofiq ma‘muriylashtirish va amalga oshirishning muhim vositasidir”. Rasmiy uslub keng va tor ma‘noda qo‘llaniladi. Keng ma‘noda rasmiy hujjatlar 2000-yil 24-avgustda Davlat Kengashi tomonidan e‘lon qilingan “Davlat ma‘muriy idoralarining rasmiy hujjatlarni tartibga solish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi qarorida belgilab qo‘yilgan 13 turdagi rasmiy hujjat, shuningdek, 1996-yil 3-mayda Xitoy Kommunistik Partiyasi Markaziy Qo‘mitasi devonxonasi tomonidan e‘lon qilingan “Xitoy Kommunistik Partiyasi davlat idoralarining rasmiy hujjatlarni tartibga solish haqida” gi Nizomida aniq ko‘rsatilgan 14 turdagi hujjatlar, shu bilan birga, umuman, partiya siyosati davlat idoralarida keng qo‘llaniladigan kundalik xizmat yozishmalarining barchasi odatda “kundalik ish yuritish hujjatlari” deb ataladi. Tor ma‘nodagi rasmiy hujjatlar deganda esa maxsus partiya va davlat idoralarining har biri belgilagan rasmiy, asosiy hujjat turlari nazarda tutiladi. Tilshunoslikda uslub (stil) termini to‘g‘risida, uni tushunish borasida turlicha fikrlar mavjud. O‘zbek tilshunosligida uslub haqida bildirilgan fikrlarni umumlashtirishga urinish va uning mukammal ta‘rifini yaratishga oid mulohazalar ham uchraydi. «*Stil* tilning jamiyat ijtimoiy faoliyatining ma‘lum tomoni bilan bog‘langan o‘ziga xos lug‘ati, frazeologik birikmalari, grammatik qurilmalari bilan xuddi shunday boshqa turlaridan, o‘z ichki xususiyatlari bilan ham tafovut qilib turuvchi podsystemasidir. Demak, har bir uslub o‘ziga xos lug‘aviy qatlami, turg‘un birikmalari, morfologik shakllari, sintaktik tuzilishi bilan farqlanib turadi.

Tilshunoslikda quyidagi uslublar ajratib ko‘rsatilganligi va yakdil fikrga kelinganligi sohada ko‘plab tadqiqotlarning yaratilishiga sabab bo‘ldi. O‘zbek tili uslublarini vazifaviy jihatdan tasnif qilish ikki omilga – til va tildan tashqarida

boʻlgan omillarga tayanadi. Bu uslublarning N. A. Baskakov, A. Sulaymonov, A. Shomaqsudov, Gʻ. Abdurahmonov, B.Oʻrinboyev, S. Muhamedovlar tomonidan tavsiya etilgan variantlari mavjud boʻlib, ularda asosan beshta uslub :

1)soʻzlashuv, 2) rasmiy (hujjat), 3) ilmiy, 4) publisistik, 5) badiiy uslublar.³

Rasmiy uslub bu davlat-maʼmuriy, huquqiy muassasalarida, rasmiy diplomatik munosabatlarida namoyon boʻladigan koʻrinishidir. Qonun matnlari, farmonlar, farmoyishlar, buyruqlar, xullas, barcha rasmiy ish qogʻozlari ana shu uslubda shakllanadi. Bu uslubning ogʻzaki va yozma koʻrinishlari, binobarin, ushbu koʻrinishlarning oʻz meʼyorlari mavjud. Jumladan, aniqlik. Ushbu uslubda shakllangan matnda noaniqlikka, izohli oʻrinlarga yoʻl qoʻyilmasligi lozim. Fikr va mazmun sodda, aniq va tushunarli tilda bayon qilinishi kerak.

Qolip soʻzlar (Klishe). Ariza, qaror, bildirishnoma, maʼlumotnoma, shartnoma, tabriknoma singari turli xarakterdagi rasmiy hujjatlarning har birining oʻziga xos bayon etish qolipi boʻladi. Ayni paytda, ularning har birining alohida soʻz va turgʻun birikmalari ham mavjud boʻladi. Rasmiy uslubdagi uchrashuvlar yoki hujjatlardagi kirish soʻzlari har bir tilda mavjud qoliplardir. Bunga salomlashish, murojaat va minnatdorchilik kabi qolip soʻzlari kiradi. Misol uchun:

尊敬的女士们先生们，你们好 [zūnjìng de nǚshì men xiānshēng men , nǐmen hǎo] – Assalomu alaykum, hurmatli xonimlar va janoblar;

尊敬的总统阁下 [zūnjìng de zǒngtǒng géxià], – Hurmatli Prezident oliyjanoblari;

尊敬的同事们，朋友们 [zūnjìng de tóngshì men , péngyǒu men]– Hurmatli hamkasblar, doʻstlar;

亲爱的乌兹别克人民 [qīnài de wūzībiékè rénmin] - Aziz oʻzbek xalqi;

亲爱的同胞们 [qīnài de tóngbāo men] – Aziz vatandoshlar;

很高兴与您会晤 [hěn gāoxìng yǔ nín huìwù] – Siz bilan uchrashganimdan bag‘oyatda mamnunman.

Shuni aytib o‘tish lozimki, so‘zlashuv uslubida huddi shu gapni 很高兴跟你见面 ko‘rinishida ifoda etiladi.

借此机会我想向您表达我的敬意 [Jiècǐ jīhuì wǒ xiǎng xiàng nín biǎodá wǒ de jìngyì] Shu fursatdan foydalanib sizga o‘zinning hurmatimni ifoda etmoqchiman.

Ushbu uslub uchun jargonlar, oddiy so‘zlashuvga xos so‘zlar, emotsional-ekspressiv bo‘yoqqa ega bo‘lgan so‘zlarning ishlatilishi me‘yor sanalmaydi va shu jihati bilan boshqa uslublardan keskin farq qiladi.

Rasmiy uslubning grammatik me‘yori ham alohida xususiyatlarga ega. Masalan, ot so‘z turkumiga oid so‘zlar ko‘p ishlatiladi. Noaniqliklarga yo‘l qo‘ymaslik maqsadida ular olmoshlar bilan almashtirilmaydi. Bu uslubda fe‘lning harakat nomi shakli faol qo‘llaniladi, gapning kesimi ko‘pincha hozirgi zamonning majhul nisbatida ifodalanadi, hujjatning xarakteriga qarab shart mayli shakliga tez-tez murojaat etiladi.

Rasmiy uslubda yozilgan matnlar uchun barcha morfologik vositalar va kategoriyalarning qo‘llanilishi bir xil darajada emas. Masalan, son va olmoshlar bu uslubda boshqa so‘z turkumlariga qaraganda ikkinchi darajali omil hisoblanadi. Rasmiy uslubning sintaktik xususiyatlari ajralib turadi. Masalan, unda darak gap, ayniqsa, qo‘shma gap shakli ko‘p ishlatiladi. Yoyiq va murakkab so‘z birikmalari mahsuldor hisoblanadi. Murakkab tipdagi nomlar keng qo‘llaniladi. Gap tuzilishida o‘zbek tilidagi odatdagi me‘yorga amal qilinadi va yuqorida sanalgan jihatlari bilan ilmiy uslubga o‘xshab ketadi.

Nutq uslublari barcha tillarda mavjud va xitoy tili bundan mustasno emas. Tilni egallashni va uni tabiiy ravishda gapirishni istagan har bir kishi uslubni o‘zlashtirishi kerak.

Rasmiy uslub.

Rasmiy uslub – (rasmiy) ish xatlarini, shartnomalarni, bitimlarni, ma'ruzalarni, umuman, hujjatlar uchun yozishda ishlatiladi.

Minimal qisqartirishlar soni va to'liq fe'l shakllaridan foydalanish rasmiy uslubning birinchi xususiyatidir.

Oddiy va murakkab takliflar rasmiy-biznes uslubining ikkinchi darajali belgisidir.

Uchinchi xususiyat norasmiy dialoglarga qaraganda uzunroq so'zlardir.

Rasmiy uslubning to'rtinchi qiziqarli xususiyati bu qisqartmalarning matnda birinchi marta eslatilishida dekodlanishi. Istisnolar bu allaqachon ma'lum bo'lgan qisqartirishlardir va shubhasiz savol tug'dirmaydi: masalan, BBC, NATO va boshqalar.

Rasmiy nutq uslubining beshinchi xarakterli xususiyati hissiy neytrallik yoki hatto fikrni taqdim etishning quruqligi va jiddiyligidir. Masalan, "?!", "!!!" belgilari. ish yozishmalarida, shuningdek, hissiy jihatdan yorqin taqqoslashlarda, metaforalarda va tasvirlarda qo'llanilmaydi.

Va nihoyat, rasmiy biznes uslubi taqdimotning anonimligini nazarda tutadi. Hujjatlarda "men ko'rib chiqaman ...", "biz ... aytamiz ..." iboralari nomuvofiqdir, rasmiy uslubga mos keladiganlar : "u ... hisoblanadi ...", "aytilgan ...".

Norasmiy aloqa uslubi.

Norasmiy uslub og'zaki tilga iloji boricha yaqin: jarangdor va sintaksis buzilishi, shaxsiy olmoshlar (masalan, "Menimcha ...", "Biz istaymiz...") va qisqartirilgan fe'llarning shakllari uning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.

Shuningdek, norasmiy yozishmalar va muloqotda jumlar ko'pincha qisqartiriladi.

Norasmiy uslubning yana bir muhim va xarakterli xususiyati - bu fe'lli fe'llardan faol foydalanish: masalan, "U urinishdan voz kechdi", "Biz yechimni ishlab chiqishimiz kerak".

Quyida rasmiy va norasmiy nutq uslublariga xos bo'lgan birikmalar va fe'llarning, shu jumladan bog'lovchi so'zlarni tanlanishini topishingiz mumkin.

Rasmiy shakli	Norasmiy shakli	Tarjimasi
会晤huiwu	见面jianmian	uchrashmoq
进行jinxing	举办juban	o‘tkazmoq
转达zhuanda	告诉gaosu	aytmoq, bildirmoq
设施sheshi	实现shixian	amalga oshmoq
筹备choubei	准备zhunbei	tayyorlanmoq
发言fayan	讲话jianghua	nutq
参与者canyuzhe, 参会者canhuizhe	参加者canjiazhe	qatnashuvchi
嘉宾jiabin	客人keren	mehmon
表示感谢您biaoshi ganxie	谢谢你xiexie ni	tashakkur, minnatdorchilik bildirmoq
与yu	和he, 跟gen	va, bilan
而er	和he	va
本ben	这zhi	mazkur, bu
将jiang	把ba	-ni (tushum kelishigi)
非常feichang	很hen	juda, bag‘oytda

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro‘yxati:

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THE CONCEPTS OF ISLAMIC BANKING

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Tashkent State University of Economics;

Omanov Husan *student of*

Corporate Governance faculty;

Email: homonov559@gmail.com

Annotation: Islamic banking is an interest free banking system and is governed by the principles laid down by Islamic Sharia'h.

Key words: commercial bank, investments, Shariah, Philosophy, Justice and Fairnes Discouraging Speculation , Maisir , Gharar , haram

Intraduction

According to Islam law, partnership are of various kinds but one best to the purpose of banking is a partnership whereby two or more people add to business, per one being an agent for the other. The capital is not necessarily to be allocate equally and profit to be divided according to the terms agreed upon between them . Under the principles of what is not forbidden is permissible , according to Musleh Uddin , an Islamic Bank may be one company , an association or a concern owned by an individual . An Islamic Bank would be a commercial bank . While the objective of the Bank would be to earn profit , it would identify it self with the Shariah as regards objectives , principles , practices and operations . Islamic bank would be undertake all normal banking business as is done by interest-based banks but the Provisions of Shariah would be kept in view at all times. The Banks would develop risk bearing but competitive products for deposits / investments wherein depositors / investors are given reasonable assurance of higher returns as also of safety of their funds . This bank would also develop innovative but competitive products for Financing which are not only compatible with Shariah but also cater to the needs of traders in the modern complex world which is ever – changing

Banking is a concept that exists in different shapes and forms in society. There are

various systems of banking across the globe. However, the most popular types of banking are conventional and Islamic banking. Regular banking operations involve borrowing money from customer deposits and lending it to make profits. The Islamic banking system works differently. The system is under the guidance of the service partnership principle, where the shareholders, borrowers, and depositors all take part in the sharing of profits and losses. What is important to note about Islamic banking is that it operates under Sharia law, and all bank operations must operate under those Islamic principles. Islamic banking has financial transaction rules known as Fiqh al-Muamalat, which is culturally different from ethical investing. For instance, investing in things such as gambling, alcohol, pork, among other forbidden items is not allowed. Islamic banking is widespread. More than 300 Islamic banks are operating in over 51 countries, the United States inclusive.

What are the Rules of Islamic Banking?

To be able to know how Islamic banking works, first you must understand the rules involved in Islamic banking. The majority of Sharia scholars agree that a commodity's credit price can exceed its cash price. So, the Islamic Fiqh Academy of Sharia Board and IOC of all Islamic banks, support the legality of this difference. Nevertheless, once there is mutual agreement about the price, no addition to the price is allowed. The main goal that Islamic banking strives to achieve is procuring money without imposing premium charges on the principal amount. Islamic banks make use of value support frameworks to realize this. The credit cash to a business and the business repays the advance without any premium.

The principles of Islamic banking operate under Sharia Law, founded on the Quran and Hadith. These are the recordings of the actions and sayings of the prophet Mohammed. So, the bankers ensure that the banking activities do not deviate from the Qurans fundamental principles. The principles are as follows:

Non-payment of interest

According to Islam teachings, lending money with interest payment is exploiting the borrower and favoring the lender. So, the Sheria law does not allow interest payment, also known as riba.

Investing in Businesses Involved in forbidden Activities

Islam teachings consider business activities such as alcohol and pork selling as haram (forbidden). Investing in these types of businesses will be going against the Sharia law. The law, therefore, prohibits Islam believers from investing in these types of business activities.

Speculation also (Maisir)

Sharia law forbids any form of gambling or assumption, which they refer to as maisir. It means that Islamic financial institutions are not allowed to be part of contracts whose owners depend on uncertain future events.

Risk and Uncertainty (Gharar)

According to the rules of Islamic finance, participating in contracts with extreme uncertainty and risk is prohibited. Muslims refer to this as gharar. The term gharar assesses the legitimacy of uncertain or threat when it comes to nature investments. The use of Gharar applies to short-selling and derivative contracts that Islamic finance prohibits. About Islamic Banking

Islamic Banking: It is defined as a banking system that conforms to the Islamic spirit, moral values and value system and is governed by the principles laid down by Islamic Shari'a. Interest-free banking is a narrow concept that refers to a number of banking instruments or transactions that avoid interest. Islamic banking, a general term, is based not only on avoiding interest-based transactions prohibited by Islamic Sharia, but also on avoiding unethical and unsocial practices. In a practical sense, Islamic banking is the transformation of ordinary monetary credit into operations based on tangible assets and real services. The Islamic banking system model leads to achieving a system that helps achieve economic prosperity.

Philosophy of Islamic Banking

The philosophy of Islamic banking is guided by Islamic Sharia. According to Islamic Shari'a, Islamic banking cannot engage in transactions involving interest/riba (an implied or required increase in the principal amount of a loan or loan). Also, they cannot engage in transactions that have an element of Gharar or Maiser. Moreover, they cannot enter into any transaction whose subject is void (forbidden in the eyes of Islam). Islamic banks focus on generating income through Shariah-compliant investment vehicles. Islamic Shari'a relates the return of capital to its efficiency. Islamic banking operations operating within the framework of Sharia are based on sharing the risks that may arise from trading and investment activities using various Islamic finance methods contracts.

Essentials of Islamic Banking

The Financial System Reform Commission, established in the State Bank of several countries, introduced Islamic financing methods, including Musharaka, Mudaraba, Murabaha, Musawama, Leasing, Salam, and others. confirmed. Exception. The Shariah Board of the Bank of States has reviewed and approved these basic principles of Islamic financing methods and recommended that the same methods be sent as guidelines to banks conducting Islamic banking business in the countries.

The advantages of Islamic banking

Justice and Fairness

The foundation of the Islamic Banking model is based on a profit-sharing principle, whereby the risk is shared by the bank and the customer. This system of financial intermediation contributes to a more equitable distribution of income and wealth

Banking for All

Although based on Shari'a principles, Islamic Banking is not restricted to Muslims only and is available to non-Muslims as well.

Transparency

Islamic Banking is about conducting business in a fair and transparent manner. Guiding you through to ensure full understanding of risks and costs associated with the products and services is the utmost prerogative.

Ethical and Moral Dimensions

The strong ethical and moral dimensions of doing business and selecting business activities to be financed play an important role in promoting socially desirable investments and better individual or corporate behaviour.

Discouraging Speculation

Speculative transactions are sources of instability and by nature is misallocation of capital. Islamic Banks are prohibited from carrying out such activities, rather focusing in deployment of capital to the real economy, to promote socio economic justice.

Conclusion : The Islamic banking system is, in principle, compatible with a close correspondence between financial and real rates of return and an efficient allocation of resources. Moreover, it could be adopted without harming the effectiveness of official supervision of financial intermediation.

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ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКАЯ МЕТОДИКА СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ ИГРЫ У СЕТКИ В ТЕННИСЕ

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Кокандский государственный педагогический институт

Доцент кафедры спортивных и подвижных игр

Муйдинов Иқболжон Абдухамидович

Аннотация. Основные технические приёмы при игре у сетки - это удары с лёта. Выходы к сетке, как правило, являются завершением атакующей комбинации, но основные сложности в выполнении самого удара связаны с его подготовкой. И причиной этому является дефицит времени.

Ключевые слова: совершенствование, физическая подготовка, вестибулярная устойчивость, эффективность.

Эксперименты показали, что время для подготовки, которым располагает теннисист, занявший позицию у сетки, составляет не более 0,1 секунды. Лимит времени во многом определяет основополагающие параметры техники ударов. В первую очередь, это широкое использование универсальной хватки для ударов справа и слева. Для техники выполнения ударов с лёта большое значение имеет также высота точки удара. При неудачном, высоком и не очень быстром ответе соперника теннисист, вышедший к сетке, для мощного завершающего удара может позволить себе рациональный для этого случая замах.

Но теннисист, находящийся на задней линии, вынужден также атаковать обводящим ударом. Сеточнику необходимо в этом случае готовиться встретить мяч в средней или низкой точке. В средней по высоте над сеткой точке, как правило, можно использовать мощный плоский удар. В таком случае для эффективного ответа поможет скорость полёта мяча обводящего удара. Необходимо направить его в не защищённое место площадки соперника, используя при этом жёсткую конструкцию (динамика движения на мяч, корпус, рука, кисть) блокирующего удара. Замах в этом случае может

привести к потере времени, более сложному выносу ракетки на мяч, сбою во всей координационной цепочке. Наиболее сложными считаются удары с лёта в низкой точке. Искусство игры с лёта в низкой точке заключается в умении не поднимать мяч высоко.

Удары с лёта разделяются на завершающие и подготовительные. С помощью первых надо стараться послать мяч вне досягаемости соперника, при вторых - как можно больше осложнить ему условия для повторной обводки. Ко вторым относятся чаще всего удары в низкой точке. Как правило, их приходится использовать в ситуациях, когда отсутствует реальная возможность немедленно «убить» мяч. Главное достоинство подготовительных ударов с лёта - существенная длина и низкий, стелящийся отскок мяча, осложняющие контратакующую обводку. В низкой точке чаще всего приходится встречать кручёный удар.

Конечная цель выхода к сетке завершающий удар с лёта. Эффективность завершающего удара в первую очередь будет зависеть насколько выше и ближе к сетке встречается мяч. Максимально выгодную точку для завершающего удара с лёта можно достичь максимально быстрым движением вперёд с последующим, если это будет необходимо, прыжком в сторону. Совершенство этих сложных ударов может быть достигнуто только том случае, когда игрок в процессе развития комбинации предугадывает направление ответного удара и начинает движение броска на мяч когда он только срывается с ракетки соперника. В этом случае мощная энергия броска через жесткую координационную цепочку, без сколько-нибудь значительного замаха, переходит в мяч.

Проблема совершенствования игры у сетки заключается в том, что в этом процессе обычно абсолютно большая часть времени отводится совершенствованию ударов с лёта. Как правило, стоя. В упражнении - «один у сетки, другой за задней линией корта». Выполнение такого удара всего лишь

фрагмент. Незначительная по времени и технической сложности часть игры у сетки.

Анализ игры у сетки ведущих молодых узбекских теннисистов показал, что техника выполнения ударов с лёта, в большинстве случаев, приемлемая. Но во время соревновательных игр большинство из них выходят к сетке эпизодически, при неизбежной позиционной необходимости. Процент выигранных мячей у сетки у тех теннисистов, которые всё-таки чаще идут вперёд, невысокий и равен примерно проценту проигранных мячей. Эти показатели не стимулируют в трудные моменты встречи двигаться вперёд. У тех теннисистов, которые избегают выходить к сетке, эти показатели ещё ниже. Возможно, горький опыт предыдущих встреч убеждает их избегать игры с лёта. Этот горький опыт с годами складывается в убеждение и усугубляется по мере перехода в следующие возрастные группы. Во взрослом возрасте, участвуя в профессиональных соревнованиях, большинству теннисистов, с такого рода подготовкой трудно подниматься вверх по рейтингу. Таким теннисистам необходимо включать в тренировочный процесс упражнения, формирующие основу технических и тактических элементов, не используемых ими в полной мере. В частности, для эффективной игры с лёта. В рекомендуемый нами комплекс входят упражнения по физической, технической, тактической и психологической подготовке.

Физическая подготовка. В связи с тем, что удары у сетки с лёта производятся в основном в движении вперёд, а часто и в прыжке и без замаха, необходимо научиться использовать энергию разбега и прыжка. Для этого нужно уметь переносить в без опорном положении центр тяжести при ударе, а с ним и энергию, заключённую в движущемся теле, на мяч.

В основу экспериментального комплекса специальной физической подготовки для совершенствования игры с лёта были добавлены, кроме типичных теннисных упражнений, используемых теннисистами для развития

спринтерской скорости, мощности толчка в различном направлении, прыжковой ловкости и вестибулярной устойчивости, гимнастические и акробатические упражнения.

Упражнения на перекладине. Раскачивание. Раскачивание с последующим прыжком на дальность.

Упражнения на кольцах. Раскачивание. Раскачивание с последующим прыжком на дальность.

— Такие же упражнения на параллельных брусьях. —

Кувырки на мате вперёд через голову.

— Прыжки с разбега на руки с последующим кувырком через голову.

Эти упражнения, по возможности от условий, желательно использовать три раза в неделю, по пол часа.

Техническая подготовка. Техника, имея в виду рисунок движения, не сложна. Но используется этот удар, как правило, в экстремальных ситуациях. Для совершенствования техники ударов при игре у сетки нужны упражнения, совершенствующие навык в сложных соревновательных ситуациях. При работе с этими упражнениями имеется в виду совершенствование многосложной теннисной реакции. Реакции разделяют на простые и сложные. Реакция легкоатлета-бегуна на старте – пример простой реакции.

Легкоатлет точно знает заранее, какой из сигналов последует и каким точно должен быть его ответ. В теннисе, да и во многих спортивных играх, всё гораздо сложнее. Как сыграет соперник, куда и как он направит мяч – каждый раз это загадка, которую нужно не только разгадать, но и на которую следует как можно быстрее отреагировать. Теннисиста, находящегося у сетки, соперник может попытаться обвести прямым ударом вдоль боковой линии, косым ударом, свечой или в редких случаях направить мяч в ноги коротко к середине сетки. Поэтому реакцию теннисиста у сетки называют трёхсложной или четырёхсложной. Именно её и нужно в первую очередь развивать.

В противном случае теннисисту грозит серьёзная опасность. Выдающиеся специалисты с большим опытом предупреждают «упражнения с односложным и двусложным реагированием, например: игра с лёта у сетки друг на друга только в заранее обусловленном направлении; или действия сеточника, при использовании против него лишь низких прямых или косых обводящих ударов при полном игнорировании свечи, способны при частом и продолжительном использовании притупить необходимые для сеточника трёхсложную и четырёхсложную реакции».

В связи с этим, при работе на совершенствование технической чистоты выполнения ударов с лёта, кроме многократного повторения упражнения один у сетки другой на задней линии, необходима работа с корзиной и тренером.

Тренер или партнёр, набрасывая мячи из корзины должен каждый раз менять направление удара (вправо, влево, свеча) и силу удара.

Таким образом, всё многообразие форм и необходимых специфических физических, психологических и технических компонентов игры у сетки совершенствуется только в процессе соревновательной встречи. А как показали наши исследования, выходов к сетке большинство теннисистов избегают. В целом всё это объясняет малый объём нестабильной и неэффективной игры у сетки ведущих молодых теннисистов Узбекистана.

Для исправления ситуации, наряду с традиционными методами совершенствования игры у сетки, описанные в многочисленных пособиях по теннису, можно рекомендовать упражнение, которое бы значительно увеличило объём соревновательной практики игры у сетки.

Суть основного тренировочного упражнения, многокомпонентной методической схемы совершенствования игры у сетки, состоит из игры со счётом соревновательного характера со специальным заданием. Игроку, выполняющему задание, необходимо играть так, чтобы мяч, посланный противником, не касался поверхности его корта. То есть все мячи, за исключением приёма подачи, он должен играть с лёта.

Ожидаемый эффект от этого упражнения - это заученное, молниеносное и точное реагирование на действия соперника при выходе к сетке в соревновательных условиях.

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INFORMATIKA VA AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARI FANINI O'QITISH JARAYONIDA MULTIMEDIA VOSITALARIDAN FOYDALANISH

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Abduhalilova Zuhra Kabuljanovna

Andijon Mashinasozlik instituti akademik litseyi

Aniq fanlar kafedrası informatika o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqoladamizda informatika va axborot texnologiyalari fani, fanni o'qitishda o'quvchilarda hosil qilinadigan kompetensiyalar haqida fikrlar keltirib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: AKT, informatika va axborot texnologiyalari, kompyuter, foto, video.

Hozirgi kunda umumiy o'rta ta'limning biror o'quv fanini to'liq ravishda yoki uning qaysi qismini AKTdan foydalanib o'tsa qanday samara berishini yoki AKTni qo'llashning pedagogik tamoyillarini, uning psixologik xususiyatlarini, uning bilish jarayoniga ta'sir qilish mexanizmi va omillarini, shuningdek yana boshqa ko'p jihatlarini kompleks tadqiq qilish dolzarb bo'lib bormoqda. Umumta'lim maktablari uchun tayyorlanayotgan multimedia vositalari, darsliklar va o'quv qo'llanmalari o'g'il-qizlarning bilimlarini yanada mustahkamlash bilan birga, pedagoglar uchun ko'makchi vazifasini ham o'tayotir.

O'rta ta'limda informatika va axborot texnologiyalari o'quv fanini o'qitishning asosiy maqsadi - o'sib kelayotgan avlodni zamonaviy axborot texnologiya vositalari bilan ishlash malakalari, mustaqil, mantiqiy va algoritmik fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirishdan iborat va olgan bilimlarini hayotda tatbiq etishga o'rgatishdan iborat.

Multimedia vositalari (multimedia - ko'pvositalilik) - bu insonga o'zi uchun tabiiy muxit: tovush, video, grafika, matnlar, animatsiya va boshqalardan

foydalanib, kompyuter bilan muloqatda bo'lishga imkon beruvchi texnik va dasturiy vositalar majmuidir.

Multimedia-gurkirab rivojlanayotgan zamonaviy axborotlar texnologiyasidir. Uning ajralib turuvchi belgilariga quyidagilar kiradi:

1.Axborotning xilma-xil turlari: ananaviy (matn, jadvallar, bezaklar va boshqalar), original (nutq, musiqa, videofilmlardan parchalar, telekadrlar, animatsiya va boshqalar) turlarini bir dasturiy maxsulotda integratsiyalaydi. Bunday integratsiya axborotni ro'yxatdan o'tkazish va aks ettirishning turli qurilmalari: mikrofon, audio-tizimlar, optik kompakt disklar, televizor, videomagnitafon, videokamera, elektron musiqiy asboblardan foydalanilgan holda kompyuter boshqaruvida bajariladi;

2.Muayyan vaqtdagi ish, o'z tabiatiga ko'ra statik bo'lgan matn va grafikadan farqli ravishda, audio va video signallar faqat vaqtning ma'lum oralig'ida ko'rib chiqiladi. Video va audio axborotlarni kompyuterda qayta ishlash va aks ettirish uchun markaziy protsessor tez harakatchanligi, ma'lumotlarni o'zlatirish shinasining o'tkazish qobiliyati, operativ (tezkor) va video-xotira katta sig'imli tashqi xotira (ommaviy xotira), hajm va kompyuter, kirish-chiqish kanallari bo'yicha almashuvi tezligini taxminan ikki baravar oshirilishi talab etiladi."Inson-kompyuter" interaktiv muloqotining yangi darajasi, bunda muloqot jarayonida foydalanuvchi ancha keng va har tomonlama axborotlarni oladi, mazkur holat ishlash yoki dam olish sharoitlarini yaxshilashga imkon beradi.

Multimedia (multi - ko'p, media - muhit) - bu kompyuter texnologiyalarining soxasi bo'lib, turli axborot saqlovchi vositalaridagi turli fizik ko'rinishda ifodalangan axborotlarga ishlov beradi.

Multimedia - bu zamonaviy texnik va dasturiy vositalardan foydalanib, interfaol dasturiy ta'minot ostida boshqariladigan video va audio effektlarning o'zaro bog'liqligi bo'lib, matn, tovush, grafika, foto, videoni birlashtiradi. Bunda ma'lumot turli axborot tashuvchilarida mavjud bo'lishi mumkin (magnit va optik disklar, audio va video tasmalar).

Multimedaning apparat dasturiy vositalari foydalanuvchi o'z ish faoliyatida axborotning matn va grafik shakldan tashqari yana foydali audio va video fayllar shakllaridan foydalanish, hamda o'zlarining animatsiyali rolik va filmlarini yaratishlari mumkin.

Hozirgi vaqtda ikkita texnologiya, sensor ekranli va elektromagnit nurlanishli texnologiyaga asoslangan interfaol doskalar ishlab chiqarilmoqda.

Sensorli elektron doska markerlar yordamida har xil foydalanuvchi interfeysini chaqirib oladigan, hajm jihatidan katta bo'lgan sensor ekrandir. Ular klassik taqdimotlarda yuqori texnologiyalar imkoniyatlari bilan birgalikda, barcha imkoniyatlardan foydalanishga sharoit yaratadi. Interfaol elektron doskalarga ulangan multimedia-proyektorlar multimediali muhitda ishlash uchun, axborotlarni internet orqali, magnitofon, kom-pyuter, DVD-disklar, flesh xotira yoki videokameralar bilan taqdimot tipida namoyish qilish uchun sharoit yaratadi.

Interfaol elektron doskalarda yozilgan barcha axborotlar ketma-ketligini kompyuterda namoyish etish uchun dasturiy ta'minotlarda imkoniyatlar ishlab chiqilgan bo'lib, bunday namoyish etishlar ham to'g'ri, ham teskari holda amalga oshirilishi mumkin.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, hozirgi axborot texnologiyalari va zamonaviy axborot tizimlari rivojlanayotgan davrda biz pedagoglarning asosiy vazifasi o'quvchilarga zamon talabi darajasidagi bilimlarni yetkazib berish hisoblanadi. Bularning barchasiga erishish uchun esa biz zamon bilan hamnafas tarzda bilimlarni va malakalarni egallab borishimiz zarurdir. Zero Birinchi Prezidentimiz aytib o'tganlariday - "Yurt kelajagi biz yoshlar qo'lidadir!".

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THE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY IS AN IMPORTANT STEP IN BUILDING A NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Nemat Khamidovich Saidakhmedov

Andijan Machine-Building Institute

Saydaliyeva Sayyora Murodali qizi

Student of Andijan Machine-Building Institute

Annotation: In this article, the author covered the ultimate goal of the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", as well as the factors underlying the determination of the fundamental goals and priorities of reforms carried out in the near future. He touched upon the impact of institutional changes in the new Uzbekistan today on economic growth and the well-being of the population, as well as the purpose and essence of the implementation of reforms aimed at balanced development of the country.

Keywords: Institute, institutional changes, economic growth, living welfare of the population, transformation of the economy

СТРАТЕГИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ – ВАЖНЫЙ ШАГ В ПОСТРОЕНИИ НОВОГО УЗБЕКИСТАНА

Саидахмедов Немат Хамидович

Андижанский машиностроительный институт

Сайдалиева Сайёра Муродали кизи

Студент Андижанский машиностроительный институт

Аннотация: В этой статье автор осветил конечную цель указа президента Республики Узбекистан "О стратегии развития Нового Узбекистана на 2022-2026 годы", а также факторы, лежащие в основе

определения основополагающих целей и приоритетов реформ, проводимых в ближайшем будущем. Он коснулся влияния институциональных изменений в новом Узбекистане сегодня на экономический рост и благосостояние населения, а также цели и сути реализации реформ, направленных на сбалансированное развитие страны.

Ключевые слова: институт, институциональные изменения, экономический рост, уровень жизни населения, трансформация экономики

Completely new institutions were created in the socio-economic life of our country in the process of economic and institutional reforms implemented step by step from the first years of Uzbekistan's independence. At the same time, an institutional environment was formed, which includes official rules determining the conduct and development of society and economy. The established institutional environment as a general institutional model determining the development of the economy of Uzbekistan had a strong impact on ownership, production and distribution relations and the establishment of a new management system. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" made it possible to understand, first of all, the fundamental goals and priority directions of the reforms to be implemented in our country in the near future, as well as the factors that are the basis for determining these goals and directions. The ultimate goal of Uzbekistan's development strategy is to further increase the well-being of the people. In order to improve the well-being of the members of society, it is necessary to implement institutional reforms aimed at balanced development of the country, to transform economic sectors and develop entrepreneurship more intensively, to unconditionally ensure human rights and interests, and to form an active civil society. The world community today is going through a complicated and conflicting period. In particular, economic processes in all regions are intensifying and intensifying, economic competition is becoming more and more serious.

Transformational processes are taking place in the social life of the countries. The configuration in the geopolitical space of the world is acquiring a completely different content and form. Even the spiritual and cultural life of nations and peoples is undergoing fundamental changes. In such a situation, in order to achieve the development of the country and increase the well-being of the people, first of all, it is necessary to ensure the continuous and stable development of the economy, strengthen its competitiveness and resistance to threats, improve the institutions of civil society, and establish the rule of law and justice in the society. very effective reforms were implemented in various fields. These reforms led to an increase in the country's economic power, strengthening of its social stability, increase in its political influence, and renewal of its spiritual space. Now Uzbekistan has all the socio-economic opportunities to achieve new goals and raise the standard of living of citizens. The goal of the development strategy to increase the well-being of the people is determined based on these possibilities. In the development strategy, it is necessary to ensure the stability of the national economy, to achieve stable growth of economic sectors, to turn the digital economy into a driver sector, to improve the investment environment, to increase financial resources, to develop entrepreneurship, to develop socio-economic regions . measures to increase the export potential are planned. Such measures will create a basis for increasing per capita income from 4 thousand US dollars by 2030.

The Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 caused our country to enter a new stage in its development - the period of establishing New Uzbekistan and creating the foundations of the Third Renaissance. At the first stage of the economic reforms implemented at this stage, special emphasis was placed on institutional changes. Abandonment of centralized planning, production, financial flows and flows of material resources by the state required a new approach to economic management. As a result of structural changes in management, the tasks of management institutions have completely changed. The administrative

management system, its control and executive institutions were completely destroyed. Redistribution tasks and their mechanisms have been abolished.

In recent years, large-scale administrative reforms have been carried out to create an effective management system, which is considered an important condition for the establishment of New Uzbekistan. In particular, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 23, 2022 "On measures to implement the administrative reforms of the new Uzbekistan" is a broad way to fully implement the ambitious idea that the implementation of administrative reforms in our country "State agencies should serve our people, not the people". revealed. The ultimate goal of the presidential decree is to create a compact public administration system that meets modern requirements in the conditions of New Uzbekistan, to increase the responsibility of the heads of state bodies and direct their activities to efficiency by simplifying the processes of decision-making and consideration of issues.

As a result of the reforms, the structure of state bodies was optimized by 15% on average by reducing the non-sectoral tasks of state bodies and introducing digital technologies into their activities, as well as reducing the positions of 40 deputy heads in 26 state bodies and organizations.

In order to reduce bureaucratic obstacles and improve the system of providing public services to the population, about 30 types of licenses and permits were canceled, more than 70 public services were simplified, and the requirement of more than 60 documents by state organizations was canceled due to the introduction of modern management principles into the activities of state bodies.

The number of users of the "Electronic Government" system has exceeded 4 million, and through it, more than 130 information resources of state agencies have been created.

About 350 types of services have been provided online on the single interactive public services portal.

The successful implementation of large-scale reforms at the modern stage of the country's development requires the creation of a completely new and effective

system of public administration. One of the main reasons why our government pays serious attention to the implementation of administrative reforms is the further reduction of administrative influence on economic sectors and the development of a healthy competitive environment of management, the expansion of market mechanisms aimed at increasing the investment attractiveness of the country and the work activity of the population. The following are planned in this direction:

- limiting the creation of state-owned commercial organizations and reorganization of existing state enterprises in areas where the private sector is effectively operating;
- development of specific market mechanisms of state participation in economic activity;
- improvement of the legal and institutional basis of social and public-private partnership in solving socio-economic issues;
- some state functions private to the sector transfer _
- Local state authority bodies financial opportunities expansion , their role and responsibility increase _
- Territorial of organs leader personnel choose and from place to place to put issues local state authority bodies powers strengthen _

As part of the administrative reforms, the executive authorities, which are being transformed, will be able to operate efficiently based on the new requirements set forth in this Decree.

By increasing the financial and institutional independence of leaders, an effective system of working with regions will be introduced.

Institutional changes alleviate certain conflicts in society, allow conflict between economic agents to be resolved through compromise, and increase the influence of new mechanisms used by the government in macroeconomic policy.

In institutional change, it is important to find answers to two questions. These are the following:

- a) successive new institutions during the transition period whether implementation will lead to economic growth;

b) introduction of new institutions during the period of stabilization of the pace of development is it appropriate?

In our opinion, institutional reforms are a continuous process. At the same time, it is necessary to constantly improve the existing institutions in order to meet the growing material and spiritual needs of the society as fully as possible.

In our country, it is necessary to strengthen the impact of institutional changes on economic growth and the improvement of the population's well-being. At the same time, it cannot be said that intensive factors of economic growth and institutional conditions are being used sufficiently. This requires bringing the initiated institutional reforms to their logical conclusion. Ensuring stable economic growth in the range of 5.0-6.0 percent creates a material basis for continuous increase of real incomes of the population of our country and significant improvement of the standard of living.

Measures aimed at strengthening the impact of institutional changes on ensuring economic growth are being taken in our country. Important reforms to achieve these goals were accelerated by the implementation of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 8, 2017 "On approval of the concept of administrative reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. PF-5185. In the concept, 6 main directions of fundamental reform of the public administration system were determined. Today, with this decree, the "Roadmap" that provides for more than 40 specific measures for the practical implementation of the norms of the concept of administrative reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan is approved and actively implemented. In addition, the activities of more than 100 state and economic management bodies have been reviewed for critical study of the state administration system and its fundamental reform, and the field is currently being improved from an organizational, structural and institutional point of view. As a result, administrative, economic and institutional reforms are gaining momentum. Also, additional conditions for ensuring economic growth are created, and the mobility and activity of society members is increasing. Institutional norms and mechanisms

create a basis for increasing the efficiency of factors affecting economic development, and create conditions for economic growth in the long term. Problems related to the formation of the institutional environment and the occurrence of institutional restrictions reduce the opportunities for economic development. Taking this into account, it is necessary to assess the quality of the institutional environment formed in the country on economic development and the impact of institutional changes on economic growth, as well as to improve the structure and mechanisms of institutions that stimulate sustainable economic development .

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FEATURES OF PRINCIPLES AND APPROACHES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF A DYNAMIC MODEL

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Yuldashev Rustam Elmurodovich

Researcher of the Karshi State University

Annotation. This article examines experience in the characteristics of principles and approaches in the development of the dynamic model of masters.

Key words: principle, synergetic, education, master, profession, personality, research, dynamics, model.

It is important to identify the preliminary theoretical model for the development of a dynamic model of masters, primarily determination of the methodological approaches of system modeling. It is advisable to use the Integrative approach in the substantiation and development of masters, taking into account the complexity and multifaceting process. In particular, the integration of the modeled system, based on systematic, competent, person-oriented and synerdiscus approaches, we believe that the integration of the modeled system.

A systematic approach is applied in the study of complex objects, at which the system of masters is one of these facilities. This approach allows disclosure of relations between the components of the system and increase their effectiveness. It is based on the following principles:

- The principle of integrity is reflecting the connection of each element within the whole system;
- compiled - the location of the system elements within a particular organizational structure and determines the analysis of their relations;
- The principle of hierarchicality - three aspects of the object: the independent system, one of the elements of the high-level system and a system of lower levels of systems;

- The principle of history is reflect the need to consider in the dynamics of development of the system and require the study of previous experiences.

Based on these principles, it is necessary to consider the master's degree as a constantly changing dynamic system consisting of higher education and a constant changes in various components. In the face of the pedagogical look: Goal, content, technological and diagnostic and diagnostic and diagnostic stations are key. In order to increase the effectiveness of the training of masters, it is necessary to pay special attention to the modeling of masters to increase the efficiency of masters and their interaction has been interacted.

In recent years, in the end of primary education, the ideas of education are being promoted and implemented through competencies through competencies. This demonstrates considering the preparation of masters based on a competent approach.

Today, knowledge shows that people should be mastered from people without being transferred to people, but also in personal career.

It is known that without forming skills and skills, knowledge cannot be used, and without them we cannot solve the problem of preparing Master's future professional career. The purpose of education is not only the knowledge and skills, but also to form support competent qualities, support competitions that need students to prepare students for modern society. The competent approach focuses on education and the result is not the amount of information learned, but the ability to act in different situations. This approach is due to the fact that the main focus is on teaching and educational content to the student and the expected results of education. The purpose of the competent approach is to provide the quality of education, which depends on modern needs and values, and reflecting its ideas about the future. [2]. As a result of the application of a competent approach, we have graduates forming specific competencies, which can determine the level of professional activities and the readiness [1].

The most important situation in the professional activity of the teacher is the research competency, in the second phase of higher education - in the second phase

of higher education - the concept of the concept of assimilation is closely linked to the concept of research activities. The success of research activities in the graduate of the master: ensures availability:

1) research activities - curiosity, interest in creative approach, the pursuit of the pursuit of the work, the pursuit of the work, the importance of creative activity, the effort of creative activities, and the perfection of creative activities;

2) creativity of thinking - the ability to promote ideas, the variances, the independence, critical thinking analysis of approaches, critical thinking analysis of approaches, critical thinking analysis of approaches.

3) the skills to study research and creating copyright methodology for research activities, and technology to create a comprehensive methodology of research and technology [4, 122- b.].

The success of the formation of research competencies that ensures the readiness of graduate graduates to research activities in many respects are determined by the introduction of the principles of individual-oriented education in the course of study. This is based on the development of each person's self-worth, individual, identity, as an individual, which has its unique subject experiences.

The essence of the person's directional approach is related to the two directions:

- The fact that the relations of teachers are directed to the establishment of an individual education model;

- Creating the learner as a subject of the educational process and to establish a study process in accordance with its personal qualities and experience.

In addition, the use of individual-oriented education involves the use of active and problematic educational methods in the pedagogical process. This will maximize the student to attract educational activities, which is very important in the master's level. Master's should learn solutions independently in developing its research abilities in problematic situations.

Approaches considered on masters Training system are expected to replenish the approaches with a synergetic approach.

According to the theory of pedagogical caterers, the Uzbek-provisions of the scientific systems are characterized by the self-organizing principles, laws of any self-organizing system, or the weakness and balancedcity.

The system of masters should be open, non-led and unbalanced, then forever, it will be effective, but also developing. The openness of the training system of masters depends in many ways to adapt quickly to its innovation, a changing information and development space, the use and development of modern educational technologies. The implementation of individual education in line with alternative strategies implies that the pedagogical process will not be linear. The continuous variation of labor market and the country's economy, the requirements of employers and science leads to the balanced state of masters training system.

Construction of the model in accordance with the principles of syneric approaches will take place in a series of stages. Initially, the bifurcation points, which include choosing one of the following subsequent education strategies, the next stage includes the pedagogical process and sustainable development, involving participational skills for the international development. In the next stage, it is necessary to create new imbalances on a certain order, after which the recipients need to change the educational trajectories. Thus, the training of masters is distinguished by the circumstances of the decision.

The fruits of the bratient training system is that the sum of all components in its accurate and logical system will yield more.

It is necessary to follow certain principles, which reflect the main doamic requirements for the preparation system of the object of the object. Systems, variations, predictions, flexibility, science, integration, stratification, consistency, and similar principles.

1. The principle of systemic principle is that the dynamic model is interrelated and presented as a single system of complement elements. The change in the status or functions of one of the elements leads to a change in the whole system. When

entering the new item or removing one of the available items, it is necessary to analyze and account for all possible consequences and effects.

2. The principle of optionality means that the model has different options in the model, which ensures the illegal and dynamics of the model.

3. Prophetic is the designation of the model to be accurate result, in our study is the formation of research competitions as a base in preparing these masters.

4. Principhurism Principhurism - The dynamic model of the training system should be built in this way that it should be possible to quickly change both the educational program and the educational goals and technology.

5. The principle of scientific activity is all elements of the model, in the process of study, is used to the use of innovative technologies and tools.

6. The principle of integration is the existence of a system that makes the system that affects the choice of necessary relations between components. In the creation of a dynamic model of the training system of primary education, integration is also used to create a single educational environment, which will create constant and comprehensive educational impact on the student.

7. The principle of stratified education is the ability to highlight micromodels that have similar characteristics within the model, but are able to operate in variable conditions.

8. Beacher principle - the elements of the dynamic model of training systems in primary education should be built on the basis of a logical structure, each of which is based on previous jars, taking into account its experience and features.

Thus, the integration of the provided methodical approaches, as well as the principles of development of primary education system, increases its efficiency and establishes its theoretically methodological basis for the development of the dynamic model of primary education.

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LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF METHODS THAT INCREASE COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

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Barno Ramizitdinovna Djamalutdinova

National institute of fine art and design named after Kamoliddin Bekhzod

Annotation: It is believed that the communicative language teaching approach is one of the most effective methods to keep away from the weaknesses of the traditional English teaching method in developing students' communicative ability. Using games, which is communicative in essence, are often considered effective in developing students' communicative ability.

Keywords: communicative ability, games, suggestions, method, technology, language, speaking.

INTRODUCTION

Sometimes it is easy to get a new method like the communicative language teaching approach heard but difficult to get it accepted, understood and applied to practical classroom teaching in the end. Therefore, it is not out of date to discuss the techniques of applying the communicative language teaching approach to classroom teaching. In this paper, the author, on the basis of pointing out the disadvantages of the traditional teaching method, discusses and explores one way to teach students effectively – using games in the English class, which is often considered as one of the best way to get the students involved in the classroom activities in which their communicative ability is practised and improved. Language games, as one of the most valuable and effective techniques in English language teaching, have been used for a long time by many western teachers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There are many good ideas about English teaching. Among these, using games in the English class is the one which is most easily accepted by students and

which is also a very useful and helpful aspect of communicative method. As is known to everyone, game is an activity providing entertainment or amusement; it's a competitive activity or sport in which players contend with each other according to a set of rules. "A game is an activity carried out by co-operating or competing decision-makers, seeking to achieve, within a set of rules, their objectives" (Rixon 2011). A game is an activity that both the teacher and students enjoy doing. It is student-centered and as appealing as playing in the playground.

Games are communicative in essence, and so using game in English teaching and learning can well realize the fundamental idea of the communicative language teaching approach. Using games is a good way to improve students' various skills, as Wright, Betteridge and Buckby (2006) say, "Games can be found to give practice in all the skills, in all the stages of the teaching and learning and for many types of communication".

As stated above, the main purpose of using games in English classes is to practise students' different skills, especially their communicative ability. Here, eight types of games from published sources are identified, discussed and explored [1,2,3].

A. *Guessing Games*

The basic role of guessing games is very simple: one person knows something that another one wants to find out. The thing to be guessed can differ greatly from game to game. It can be a word, an object, an activity or many other things. Guessing games are useful in helping students practise logical thinking and asking questions. 3-item story is one example of a guessing game. One person in a group knows the story in which there are three items given to the other members of the group. *Picture Games*

Picture games include several types:

Comparing and contrasting pictures; Considering differences or similarities;
Considering possible relationships between pictures, such as narrative sequence;

Describing key features so that someone else may identify them or represent

them in a similar way; Making a story according to the given picture.

Most of these picture games involve the learners in the relatively free use of all the language at their command and at the same time give them the opportunity to practise their speaking and listening.

B. *Sound Games*

Sound effects can create in the listeners' mind an impression of people, places and actions. There is a demand for the listener to contribute through the imagination. This inevitably leads to individual interpretations which mean that the listeners can exchange their points of view and express opinions and ideas. This kind of games can stimulate students' imagination and thinking, and offer them a chance to practise their listening and speaking. Students can make guess at the object described by sound, or make dialogue or a story.

C. *Mime*

Mimes can be done in pairs, groups or even by the whole class. One side has to perform the mimes for the other side so that the answer can be found. It can be an object, action or person. So miming activities are valuable language-learning situations. Guessing something is linked with the real desire to find out and thus is a true communication situation. Miming trains the students' skill of observation and improvisation. It emphasizes the importance of gesture and facial expression in communication. *Fact-finding Games*

This mainly deals with general knowledge and is a very practical exercise. Everyday, there is something important happening, so the students can be asked what happened on a day in history. It may be a historical accident, a birthday of a famous person, or something strange or marvelous. Then further details can be asked. The students can discuss in pairs or groups in order to find much more information.

D. *Debates*

In this activity, a topic is given and two sides are set up, one supporting the idea and the other opposing it. Then they argue giving their evidence. The aim of

this activity is to get the students to talk and stimulate their interest and competitive spirit. Such activities make the students think about their values and priorities. There is no doubt that this activity will improve students` conversation and eloquence.

E. Role Plays

Role plays often consist of short scenes, which can be realistic or pure fantasy. Role plays may be enacted around everyday situations as well as around topical problems. One easily-obtained role play is from the text, which may be actual role play material.

CONCLUSION

From the above analysis, a conclusion can be drawn that teaching and learning English by means of language games is effective and efficient in improving students` communicative ability. While in the traditional method of teaching English, students sit still listening to teachers talking about English language and try their best to remember English words and grammatical rules by rote memory, in the communicative language teaching approach they are actively involved in playing games which in turn can arouse and maintain their interest in learning, promote their motivation of study, and at the same time get lots of opportunities to have their basic skills of listening and speaking practiced.

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O'ZBEK XALQ DOSTONLARIDA VOQELIK TASVIRI

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Djurakulova Gulnoza Shavkatovna

– *O'zbekiston jurnalistika va
ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar universiteti*

katta o'qituvchisi, Phd

Maqoladan ko'zda tutilgan maqsad o'zbek xalq og'zaki ijodidagi ot obrazining nomlari, ularning tuslaridan olinishi, qahramonlar va otlarning o'ziga xos, nazarkarda yoki ilohiy bo'lishi tasviri barcha turkiy xalqlar eposlariga xos ekanligi yarim bosma taboq hajmli ilmiy maqolada tadqiq etishdir. Maqolada analitik, tarixiy-qiyosiy tahlil metodlaridan foydalaniladi.

Kalit so'zlar: turkiy xalqlar, folklor, epos, o'zbek xalq dostoni

O'zbek xalq dostonlarida voqelik tasviri: boshlamalar, qahramonlar ta'rif-tavsifi, xatti-harakati, nutq murojaati, holat-kechinmalari, doston yakuni ma'lum epik formulalar vositasida kuylanadi. Bu xil epik formulalar baxshi-shoirlarning ijro jarayonida voqelikni to'laqonli tasvir etishida tayanch ifoda vositasi sifatida muhim rol o'ynaydi. Doston syujeti tashkil etuvchi motivlarning mukammal badiiy tasvir olishida epik formulalar baxshilar uchun epik bilimni mustahkam saqlab turuvchi, unga badiha imkoniyatini beruvchi barqaror andoza sanaladi. Bular asarning kirish qismi, alp, pari, sanam, ot ta'rifi, ot egarlash, nasihat, kuzatish, safar kosasi, may tutish (allayor), yo'l tasviri, poyga, jang, yakun kabi an'anaviy tasvir o'rinlaridir. Xalq dostonlarida keluvchi epik formulalar tarkibida "ot ta'rifi" tasviri deyarli barcha epos namunalarida yetakchi o'rin tutishi bilan ham ajralib turadi.

Azaldan dostonda bahodir bor, ot bor, ularning o'zaro munosabati bor, zero qahramonning barcha yumushlari bevosita ot bilan bog'liq. Shuning uchun dostonda ot obraziga katta o'rin beriladi, ularning tarixi va tavsifi keltiriladi va tabiiyki, ot bilan bog'liq formulalar keng o'rin tutadi. Bu fikrni o'zbek folklorshunosligimiz asoschisining quyidagi fikrlari ham tasdiqlaydi. "Dostonlarda

ot juda muhim o'rin egallaydi. U qahramonning muvaffaqiyatga erishuvi yo'lida xizmat qilib, g'oyat mushkul vazifalarni bajaradi, qahramonga katta yordam beradi. Qahramon otga minganligi tufayli istagiga erishadi. Shu narsa xarakterliki, epik ot qatnashmagan bironta qahramonlik dostonini topish qiyin. Ot qahramonning safari va kurashlarida doimiy yo'ldoshi, ishonchli qo'ldoshi va do'stidir. Bahodir otning sifatlari dostonlarimizdagi voqealar davomida tadrijiy takomillashib, unitilmas epizodlarning markaziy figuralaridan biriga aylanadi. O'zbek dostonlarida ot obrazi ba'zan bosh qahramon darajasiga ko'tariladi".

Folklorshunos A. Tilovov turkiy xalqlar adabiyotida maxsus ot, uning vasflari, hayotda tutgan o'rni, ranglari, yurish shakllari, ot boqish, tarbiyalash, ot hastaliklari, ularni davolash yo'llari, ot tanlash haqidagi "Baytarnoma" nomi bilan ataluvchi yozma asarlar mavjudligini ko'rsatib o'tgan.

O'zbek xalq dostonlarida ham epik ot obrazi o'ta mukammal darajada ishlangan. Ayniqsa, G'iro't, Boychibor kabi jangovor ot obrazlarini xalq baxshilari mahorat bilan badiiy jihatdan tugal ta'riflashgan. "Ot ta'rifi" tasvirining eng mashhur va go'zal namunasi bu "Go'ro'g'li" dostonlarida keladigan nazarkarda G'iro't ta'rifidir. G'iro'tga nazarkarda ta'rifi berilishiga asos mavjud. "Shu ahvolda yurib edi, buni Xizr bildi. U, Go'ro'g'libek endi toyni chopib yomon o'rgandi. Yana bir chopsa qizil moy qilib, ishdan chiqarib qo'yadi, Buning toyini olib kelay, o'zim boqib beray, bo'lmasa Go'ro'g'libek otsiz bo'lib qoladi, dedi"...Olib ketib Xizr boqdi .

"Go'ro'g'libek ham qirq chiltanlarga qo'shildi. Shunda hazrat Qutbil Axtab aytdilar: "Go'ro'g'li sharob antaxurni ichib sohibqiron bo'ldi. Sohibqironlikni G'iro't ko'tara olmaydi. Endi G'iro'tga ham bir kosa maydan beringlar", – dedi. Go'ro'g'libekning G'iro'tiga ham bir kosa sharobdan suvga qo'shib berdilar. Shunda Go'ro'g'libek qip-qizil valiolloh bo'lib, yetti qat osmonni, yetti qat yerni, Govimohni ham ko'rdi".

Folklorshunos olim Sh. Turdimov "Go'ro'g'li dostonlari genezisi va ularning tadrijiy bosqichlari" asarida epik qahramon va epik ot taqdir chiziqlari deyarli bir-

biriga mos kelishini aytib o'tadi. Demak, G'irotdan ham chiltonlar bergan sharobni ichib ular qatoriga qo'shilgan Go'ro'g'liga munosib tulpor bo'lishi shart.

Keksa chavandozlarning guvohlik berishicha, zotdor va dongdor otlar, haqiqatdan ham gapga tushunadi, ba'zan sharoit taqozosi bilan egasining otga yulvorishi, otni maqtashi tufayli otga g'ayritabiiy kuch keladi va boshqa paytda uddasidan chiqolmagan ishlarni hayratomuz tarzda bajaradi. Bu holat xalqimiz sevib kuylovchi dostonlarimizda ham o'z aksini topadi.

“Otda ta’rifi” tasvirining doston uchun ahamiyatli bo’lgan tomoni shundaki, bunda qahramon otda ta’rifining sifatleri, belgilari, qilgan ishlari sanab o’tiladi. Bu tasvir

- qahramon yoki tulpor bilan munosabatga kirishish uchun vosita sifatida
- ot egarlash jarayonining yakunida, ya’ni tulpor jangovor holga kelganida;

- safar oldidan;
- safar mobaydida otdan yanada ko’proq shijoat, tezlik kutilayotganda;
- qahramon otda ta’rifining hatti-harakati, sadoqati yoki u tufayli erishilgan g’alabalardan zavqlanganda;
- otdan ma’lum bir vazifani bajarish so’ralganda qo’llaniladi.

Masalan, “Go’ro’g’lining paydo bo’lishi” Ahmadjon Soyibnazarov variantida keltirilgan “ot ta’rifi” tasvirini ko’rib chiqamiz:

Qizlar yaqin kelib qaradi. Yunus pari qarasa, ot bo’ynining o’ng tomonida yozilgan: “Otda – G’irko’k, ustidagi Go’ro’g’libek, tikilgani tosh ham bo’lsa tars yorilsin”. Uni parilar o’qib ko’rdilar, “Bul ot odamxo’r, hech narsa qoshiga borolmaydi. Kelinglar bir ish qilaylik. Otni ta’riflab egasining qoshiga boraylik. Agar yomonlik xayolga kelsa bul ot odamni o’ldirsa o’ldirar, magar egasi otiga o’rgatgan bo’lsa, hech hiylayu nayrang qilib bo’lmaydi”, – deb Yunus pari otga qarab bir so’z deb turgan edi:

Mash’alday yonib ko’zlaring,

Shamolga tovlanur kokiling.

Qarasam bordur ko’k xoling,

Manjaday kelar orqa doling...” .

Bu misralarda qahramon yoki tulpor bilan munosabatga kirishish uchun vosita sifatida keltiriladigan “ot ta’rifi” formulasini ko’rishimiz mumkin.

“Tarkibaxshon” dostonida Avaz sheriklari bilan yo’lni yo’qotib to’g’ri yo’lni topishni dono G’irotdan so’raydigan o’rni bor. Ayni shu o’rinda

Jonim G’irot, molim G’irot,
Sen mingan topgan murod,
Aylanayinda joningdan,
Karomatingni bir ko’rsat,
Eli xalqimning davlati,
Sulton otamning G’iroti.

misralari bilan boshlanuvchi 16 bandlik she’r keltiriladi. Bunda tulpordan juda muhim vazifani bajarish so’ralmoqda va ta’rif keltirilmoqda .

Po’lkan baxshi kuylagan Go’ro’g’lining tug’ilishi” dostonida esa ot ta’rifi tulpordan ko’proq shijoat so’rab keltiriladi.

Dushman bilan bo’ldim taraf,
Arzimni aytay senga qarab,
Otim G’irot, jonim G’irot,
Yeming kishmish, to’rvang banot,
Tezgir bo’lgin, keldi arab!

O’ttiz besh misradan iborat yuqoridagi band bilan boshlanuvchi she’riy parchada “Otim G’irot, jonim G’irot, Yeming kishmish, to’rvang banot, Tezgir bo’lgin, keldi arab!”misralari har bandning so’ngida takrorlanadi. Bu she’riy parchada ritm hosil qilib, u ifodalayotgan holatni, ya’ni qahramonning dushman bilan yuzma-yuz kelishidan avvalgi holatdagi kuchli his-tuyg’uni yorqin ifodalaydi. Misralarning sakkiz bo’g’inli ekanligi, (4+4)taktdan tashkil topishi, so’z takrori she’riy parchaning ravon va tez o’qilishiga va tinglovchining qahramon va otning tezligini his qilishiga sabab bo’ladi. Yuqorida keltirilgan “Otim G’irot, jonim

G'irof" misrali formula eng ko'p qo'llaniladigan va ko'p variantli epik formulalar sirasiga kiradi.

Albatta, bu badiiy tasvir o'rinlari ham shunchaki qo'llanilmay, otning kuch qudratini ifodalashda yordamchi komponent bo'lib hizmat qilish bilan birga dostonni yanada qiziqarli chiqishini ta'minlovchi detalъ vazifasini bajaradi. Bu badiiy tasvir vositalarining o'z o'rnida va mukammal tarzda ishlatilishi, shubhasiz, xalq dostonchisining badiiy mahoratini namoyon etadi. Baxshi bunday an'anaviy o'rinlarni kuylaganda o'zining epik xotirasiga suyanadi va undagi tayyor epik formuladan foydalanadi.

ВОСПИТАНИЕ ПОДРАСТАЮЩЕГО ПОКОЛЕНИЯ.

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Абдиева Дилфуза

старший преподаватель

кафедры «Социальные науки»

Каршинский инженерно-экономический институт (Узбекистан)

Аннотация Актуальность данной проблемы заключается в том, что характеристика психологическая структура педагогической деятельности учителя средней школы применима и для деятельности преподавателя вуза, ибо это тоже профессиональная деятельность

Ключевые слова Личность, деятельность, особенность, процесс, способность, формироваться, нравственные, умственная, политическая, мировоззрения

EDUCATION OF YOUNGER GENERATION

Abdiyeva Dilfuza

Senior Lecturer Department of "Social Sciences"

Karshi engineering and economics institute (Uzbekistan)

Annotation The relevance of this problem lies in the fact that the characteristic psychological structure of the pedagogical activity of a secondary school teacher is also applicable to the activities of a university teacher, because this is a professional activity.

Keywords Personality, activity, feature, process, ability, form, moral, mental, political, worldview.

Президент Республики Узбекистан Шавкат Мирзиёев отметил, – “что в нашей стране большое внимание уделяется воспитанию подрастающего поколения. В результате последовательной реализации государственной политики, направленной на решение жизненно важных вопросов молодёжи, наши юноши и девушки добиваются огромных успехов во всех сферах”. [1]

Для эффективного выполнения стоящих перед учителем задач студент педагогического вуза еще в стенах института должен овладеть профессионально-педагогическими знаниями, умениями и навыками, личностными качествами учителя советской школы – наставника учащейся молодежи. Профессиональные и личностные, в том числе и нравственные, качества будущего учителя формируются под влиянием объективных и субъективных факторов воспитания. При этом, несомненно, большая роль принадлежит важным факторам нравственного воспитания студентов.

В Узбекистане с руководством Президента Ш. Мирзиёева уделяется особое внимание воспитанию гармонично развитого молодого поколения. «В старших классах дети формируются как личности, сплачиваются в команде», сказал глава нашего государства. Именно в этот период их нельзя отлучать от адаптированной, привычной для них среды. Это может негативно повлиять на психологию молодежи, ее посещаемость занятий, в конечном итоге – на уровень образования и воспитания. Поэтому необходимо обеспечить непрерывность образовательного процесса, совершенствовать учебные программы. [2]

Данная характеристика психологической структуры педагогической деятельности учителя средней школы применима и для деятельности преподавателя вуза, ибо это тоже профессиональная деятельность. Однако объект деятельности преподавателя вуза – студент, цель – подготовка специалиста. Поэтому она имеет и свои особенности. Педагогическая деятельность преподавателя вуза рассматривается как процесс решения бесчисленного ряда педагогических задач. Основная из них, выступающая как конечная цель обучения и воспитания в вузе, решается преподавателем путем преобразования обучения студентов в самообучение, внешней регуляции их действий и поступков в само регуляцию. Структура знаний педагога вуза включает систему политических знаний. Осуществление учебно-воспитательного процесса в высшей школе означает постоянное

взаимодействие преподавателя со студентами. Для того чтобы нравственное воздействие было плодотворным, преподавателю необходимо знать особенности студенческого возраста.

Средняя школа, систематически развивая все стороны умственной деятельности учащихся, готовит их к жизни и труду, занятиям в высшей школе. Такие качества, как способность к анализу и синтезу, к абстракции и обобщению, начинают формироваться в средней школе, а основательно развиваются в вузе. [3] Вместе с тем у юноши 18 лет наблюдается определенная умственная и общественно-политическая зрелость. Но перед ним в педагогическом вузе встают новые, сложные задачи, которые связаны с овладением педагогической профессией.

Студента вуза характеризует способность к критическому рассуждению. Юность-время самоанализа и самооценок. Нередко у первокурсника наступает перелом-от восторженного состояния при поступлении в вуз к скептическому отношению к новому режиму, к ряду преподавателей. Как известно, в условиях стремительного научно-технического и социального прогресса человек принимает огромное количество информации.

Неизмеримо ныне расшились каналы получения знаний. И преподаватель для студента теперь-не единственный источник информации. Наряду с этим следует также иметь в виду, что в наши дни любому абитуриенту открыты двери во все вузы, а само высшее образование потеряло ореол исключительности, каким оно было окружено еще четверть века тому назад. [4] Не секрет, что иногда юноша или девушка идет в вуз лишь потому, что ему «неудобно остаться без высшего образования, так как все его сверстники учатся». Это одна сторона вопроса. Но есть и вторая, не менее важная сторона. В наше время учебно-воспитательные задачи значительно углубились и усложнились. В учебно-воспитательном процессе преподаватель вуза выступает как носитель нравственных знаний, моральных

принципов и норм поведения, как носитель нравственных представлений, идеалов, взглядов, чувств, и убеждений. [5]

В научно-педагогической и общественной деятельности он выступает как человек, преподающий систему нравственных и профессионально- педагогических понятий, как человек, осуществляющий нравственное просвещение.

Для повышения эффективности влияния личности преподавателя вуза как воспитателя нравственности его научно-педагогическая деятельность должна отвечать определенным требованиям. От него требуется сочетать в себе политические, деловые, научные и моральные качества. Необходимость сочетания этих высоких качеств вытекает из той роли, которую играет преподаватель не только в обучении, в передаче профессиональных знаний, но и в формировании мировоззрения, в политическом и нравственном воспитании студенческой молодежи. Важное значение в облике преподавателя имеют его моральные и нравственные качества, его эрудиция, образованность, интеллигентность, знание не только своего предмета, но и литературы, искусства, его жизненный опыт. [6]

Общие качества, необходимые для формирования умений самостоятельной познавательной деятельности, вырабатываются прежде всего всем комплексом учебно-воспитательных воздействий. Разносторонность знаний, высокая культура преподавателя важнейшие условия воздействия на нравственный облик будущего учителя.

Настоящий преподаватель не может замыкаться в узкую область своей науки. Политическая жизни, художественная литература, живопись, театр, кино, музыка, архитектура, спорт-все это должно находиться в поле зрения преподавателя- наставника. [7]

Всем этим он должен заразить студентов – будущих воспитателей подрастающего поколения. Деятельность тех и других проходит относительно самостоятельно, но в то же время представляет собой

органическое единство: единые цели, единый план действий, общие условия и.т.д. Если разорвать эту взаимосвязь, это единство, прекращается и сам педагогический, воспитательный процесс.

Такова объективная закономерность. Эта закономерность продолжает действовать не только при непосредственном общении преподавателя и студента, но и при опосредствованных отношениях, когда используются различные формы связи, когда имеется какой-то посредник в передаче информации.

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AMIR TEMUR'S PREPARATIONS FOR THE INDIAN MILITARY CAMPAIGN

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Bukhara Pedagogical Institute teacher **Kenjayev Sardor**

Student of group 1-Itar22. **Melsova Shahina, Yusupjonova Marjona,**

Raupova Nozigul, Rahmatov Murod

Anotatsiya: This article discusses Amir Temur's military campaign to India and the factors that led to it.

Kays words: China, India, elephant, forest, river, fighting elephant, sword, navkar, sipohi, kanbuls

Amir Temur's military goal and prepared army was intended to be mobilized for the Chinese campaign. However, Prince Muhammad Sultan had to prepare the material base for this campaign - food and fodder. Yazdi also testifies about this: "I was doing azimat in Sahibqiran ul Mahal, go to the infidels of China." When Amir Temur was preparing to go to China, his beggars persuaded him to go to India. At the end of March 1398, he went on a march to India. Mrs. Saraymulk and Ulug'bek also set out with the hosts. After crossing Amudarya, Shahrukh from Herat also joins with his soldiers and stays with his father and son until the middle of August. Amir Timur spends several months fighting with the infidels of old Kafiristan (now Nuristan) in the Hindu Kush mountains in northern Afghanistan before crossing to India. Then in August he will come to Kabul through Andarob. In the middle of this month, he returned Shahrukh to Herat and Ulugbek and Mrs. Saraymulk to Samarkand, and on August 20, he left Kabul and headed for India. He passed away on November 21, 1221 after a battle with Sultan Jalaluddin Khorezmshah Genghis Khan from the Sind River on September 24. At that time, the deserts on the left bank of the river were called Jalali desert. This testified that Amir Temur himself was aware of the history and events of Jalaluddin Khorezmshah, and that memories of the great Khorezmshah were alive in these lands during his time. The battle with

Delhi Sultan Sultan Mahmud Khan Dehlavi will take place on December 17, 1398. Ten thousand cavalry, forty thousand foot and one hundred and twenty elephants will take part in the Indians. Special swords were attached to both tusks of the elephants, and they were trained to swing this sword. In addition, a bronze throne was placed on top of the elephant, and five or six archers were sitting on it.

Between the two elephants, the ball and Hazrat Sahibtsiron's great desire never stopped for a day or night from expanding the sphere of rule and sweeping the territory of the country. Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi was the gunner. The elephants were also clothed. The owner is also well prepared for the battle. He built a fortress of reeds and wood in front of the army. Then the army dug a trench around it and tied the edge of the trench tightly with Indian sheepskin. In addition, Sahibqiran made many iron spikes against elephants. Balls were equipped. The battle did not last long. The enemy could not withstand the attack and pressure of the Chigatai and scattered. Sahibqiran performed the midday prayer near the Delhi Gate. In the battle, the sixteen-year-old Prince Khalil Sultan showed great heroism. Sultan Mahmud Khan Dehlavi was completely defeated and fled. Sahibqiran returned from an eleven-month Indian campaign in the spring of 1399. During his campaign in India, Amir Timur made the intention that if he returns to Samarkand safely, he will build a mosque. Therefore, he ordered to build a mosque in Samarkand. On May 10, 1399, the design of the mosque was drawn up, and two hundred master masons brought from Persia, Azerbaijan and India started work on the same day. Five hundred men were sent to the mountain to cut stone. Ninety-five elephants brought from India were used to bring stone from the mountain.

All the architects and craftsmen known in the country were engaged in work. A prince and a bek were appointed as collectors for each work, apparently, the person in this position was the financial provider of this work. Yazdi writes, "I was very caring of the owner. He was not involved in the work of the mosque, but he came every day and took care of the workers." And most of the avqots were standing in the Khanim madrasa or Tuman Agha's house and praying. On Friday, four

hundred and eighty columns of stone were built, each of which was seven cubits (3.5 meters) long. And they made the roof (ceiling) of stone. After the completion of the mosque, Dilkusho went to the garden and gave weddings. He dressed the craftsmen in robes and put them on horses. At this time, they reported that there was a ruckus in Tabriz related to Prince Mironshokh. At that time, Mironshokh was heavily addicted to alcohol and spent more time with good friends, drunkards and gambling. He even scolded the proud Khanzoda once and even beat him. Khanzoda could not bear this and immediately left for Samarkand in anger. Khanzoda came to Sahibkiran when he received bad news about the situation in Tabriz and said: "If Sahibkiran does not follow his advice, he will do it." My lord, His Highness, took possession of it and distributed everything to his beggars. In the center, the main victory flag of the army was attached to the hand. In front of the ranks of the army, thirty war elephants, captured during the Indian campaign, were lined up.

Various goods from different countries - "China, India, Tatarstan and other countries" were brought to the annual fairs held in Samarkand. During the Timurid period, the exchange of products made by Mowarounnahr and Indian artisans was quite lively. From India, thin white fabrics woven with darning, gazmols called Hyderabad, Gujarat, Banoras fabrics depending on the place of manufacture, as well as sugar. and dyes were brought. Such relations with India developed especially during the period of Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur.

It should be noted that Amir Temur had a habit of celebrating every triumphant and joyful event by building a magnificent architectural monument. For this purpose, skilled builders brought from India, famous master craftsmen from Khorezm, Isfahan, Shiraz, Aleppo and many other cities of the East built beautiful structures in the country.

Every architectural monument built in Samarkand during the time of Amir Temur, from the foundation to the top of the dome, from the tiles to the bricks, had a single, complete and perfectly beautiful appearance. Also, large-scale monumental paintings were painted on the walls of many palaces built during this period. In them,

Amir Temur's triumphant campaigns to India, Iran and Dashti Kipchak, reception ceremonies of ambassadors, conversations with scholars and scholars, wedding and party scenes were very skillfully depicted.

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COMPARATIVE CLASSIFICATION OF COMPOUND SENTENCES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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To‘xtaboyev Hayitali Hamdamboy o‘g‘li

A student of FerSU

Uktamova Mohigul Khamidullo-kizi

English teacher, Fergana state university

Annotation: When defining a compound sentence, some English scholars have it and focus on the number of cuts, some focus on the number of simple sentences in the compound sentence, and still others combine the two. The theory of compound sentences in English was fully formed in English normative grammar in the second half of the 19th century and has remained unchanged to this day. This article discusses the comparative analysis of English compound sentences in Uzbek.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, at a time when international dialogue and relations are wide open, translations of English compound sentences are developing. This is evidenced by the fact that English phrases and words have entered the Uzbek and other languages. Learning English is a topical issue for Uzbek youth today. This issue, which is still relevant today, was on the agenda of our ancient ancestors. For example, Farobi knew more than seventy languages, Osman Nasir translated an entire work by heart, and Navoi and other scholars wrote in two languages.⁴

MAIN PART

In the following examples, we will look at the similarities and differences between English and Uzbek compound sentences, the contextual relationship between them, and the word order in sentences in two languages:

⁴ G'apparov M. «Ingilz tili grammatikasi» Toshkent 2006. 336 p.

«The city was very nice and our flat was very fine» - "Shahar juda chiroyli edi va bizning kvartiramiz juda yaxshi edi".

The compound sentence in English has been translated into Uzbek as a compound sentence without a conjunction. In the English compound sentence, "The city" is the owner of the first sentence, and "was" is the participle of "and", which connects two simple sentences, the determinant, "flat" is the owner of the second sentence, "was very fine."

By the 1970s, while studying compound sentences, Ilish had explored the main differences based on which clause they were related to. According to the scholar, some compound sentences are connected by a connecting word according to their function and its meaning is determined, while others do not require such words when connected. A conjunction is a synonym that is not a conjunction. However, the scientist calls both of them a compound sentence because they contain several components.⁵

The English scholar Ilish at that time considered the problem of converting homogeneous parts into compound sentences. He said, "I met my relatives and friends would be said to have been 'contracted' out of two sentences: 'I met my relatives, and I met my friends'".⁶

There are two bases in the study of sentence, which is one of the components of language, in particular, in the study of conjunctions:

- a) the basis of having widespread popularity;
- b) by the way, the basis of the cut with a number of exceptions.

The first direction is based on and connected with the modern doctrine of simple speech. With the doctrine of European linguistics, which re-acquired this direction in the middle of the twentieth century, that a sentence must consist of two parts, that there can be no ownerless sentences, the judgment of logic consists of two

⁵ Ganshina M.A. Vasilevskaya N.M. «English grammar» M., Higher school publishing house 1964 598 p.

⁶ Ilish B. «The structure of Modern English» Leningrad 1971. 366 p.

parts - the subject and the predicate. consisted of the doctrine of the subordination of the subject and the subordination of the predicate.

Subject clause

“What was important to him was matrimony”- *“Uning uchun muhim bo’lgan narsa nikoh edi”*. "What was important to him" is the following sentence, "was matrimony" is the main sentence. We define this by asking questions, because the question is always asked from the main sentence, and the subordinate clause is determined by determining which part of the sentence is in the main sentence, interpreting and completing it.

Predicative clause

«The fact was, she did not understand us» - *“Shu aniqki, u bizni tushunmadi”*.

In this example, "the fact was" is the main sentence, "she did not understand us" is the participle.

Object clause

“I don’t know what he is talking about” – *“U nima haqida gapirayotganini bilmayman”*.

In this example, "I don't know" is the main sentence.

Attributive clause

«The woman who was here yesterday is a tailor» - *“Kecha bu yerda bo’lgan ayol tikuvchi edi”*.

In this example, "The woman is a tailor" is the preposition, followed by the pronoun "who was here yesterday" which defines the word "the woman" in the preposition.

Translation difficulties are not limited to linguistic differences. Sometimes the problem of translating from a new language is more complicated than from a long language. Although the languages to be translated or to be translated are lexically-grammatically and structurally distant from each other, the problem of translation is that if they feel similarity, commonality, harmony, commonality in terms of subject,

literary tradition, stage of cultural development of two languages the possibility of a successful solution arises.

Language is one of the most important indicators of a work of art. In translation, this main factor changes, one language is replaced by another, and as the language changes, there is sometimes a phenomenon of methodological shift. In many cases, the interpreter himself consciously allows this to happen, using it as a precaution.

«I hope he's not ill» - «Ishqilib betob emasmi?»

According to AV Fedorov, “translators often face the problem of reflecting the rhythm of translation in the translation of prose works. However, this feature, reflected in the work of each writer, is based on the lexical-phonetic, grammatical-structural means of the language, which in the process of translation should not be copied blindly. In translation, each writer's style must be re-created, taking into account the capabilities and characteristics of the other language. ”

Conjunctions used in English are not essentially different from conjunctions used in other languages. There is a lot of artistic style in the use of compound sentences. It is also interesting that the content relations are presented in different languages by the same device or by another device, as well as the material in which the sections are expressed in English and Uzbek. The content expressed in English sources is not always available in Uzbek versions.

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РАЗВИТИЕ ТВОРЧЕСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА

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Кокандский государственный педагогический институт

Доцент кафедры спортивных и подвижных игр

Муйдинов Икболжон Абдухамидович

Аннотация. Данной статье речь идет о роли и влиянии изобразительной деятельности на воспитание и развитие ребенка дошкольного возраста, о видах занятий изобразительной деятельностью, включающих рисование, лепку, аппликацию и конструирование.

Ключевые слова: воспитание, развитие, деятельность, обучение, действие.

Процесс обучения должен быть направлен на развитие детского творчества, на творческое отражение впечатлений от окружающего мира, от произведений литературы и искусства. Рисование, лепка, аппликация – виды изобразительной деятельности, основное назначение которой – образное отражение действительности. Творческая деятельность – одна из самых интересных вида деятельности для детей дошкольного возраста.

Творческая деятельность – это специфическое образное познание действительности. Как всякая познавательная деятельность имеет большое значение для умственного воспитания детей.

Овладение умением изображать невозможно без целенаправленного зрительного восприятия – наблюдения. Для того чтобы нарисовать, вылепить какой-либо предмет, надо предварительно хорошо с ним ознакомиться, запомнить его форму, величину, цвет, конструкцию расположение частей.

Для умственного развития детей имеет большое значение постепенное расширение запаса знаний на основе представлений о разнообразии форм

пространственного расположения, предметов окружающего мира, различных величинах, многообразии оттенков цветов.

При организации восприятия предметов и явлений важно обращать внимание детей на изменчивость форм, величин (ребенок и взрослый), цветов (растения в разные времена года), разное пространственное расположение предметов и частей (птица сидит, летает, клюет зерна, рыбка плавает в разных направлениях и т.д.); детали конструкций также могут быть расположены по-разному.

Занимаясь рисованием, лепкой, аппликацией дети знакомятся с материалами (бумага, краски, глина, мел и др.), с их свойствами, выразительными возможностями, приобретают навыки работ. Обучение творческой деятельности без формирования таких мыслительных операций, как анализ, сравнение, синтез, обобщение.

На основе сходства предметов по форме возникает общность способов изображения в рисунке, лепке. Например, чтобы слепить ягоду, орешек, неваляшку, яблоко или цыпленка (предметы имеющие круглую форму или части круглой формы), необходимо раскатать кусочки пластилина или глины кругообразными движениями.

Способность анализа развивается от более общего и грубого различения до более тонкого. Познание предметов и их свойств, приобретаемое действенным путем, закрепляется в сознании.

На занятиях по творческой деятельности развивается речь у детей: усвоение и название форм, цветов и их оттенков, пространственных обозначений способствует обогащению словаря; высказывания в процессе наблюдений за предметами, при обследовании предметов, построек, а также при рассматривании иллюстраций, репродукций с картин художников положительно влияют на расширение словарного запаса и формирование связной речи.

Как указывают психологи, для осуществления разных видов деятельности, умственного развития детей большое значение имеют те качества, навыки, умения, которые они приобретают в процессе рисования, аппликации и конструирования.

Творческая деятельность тесно связана с сенсорным воспитанием. Формирование представлений о предметах требует усвоения знаний об их свойствах и качествах, форме, цвете, величине, положении в пространстве. Дети определяют и называют эти свойства, сравнивают предметы, находят сходства и различия, то есть производят умственные действия.

Таким образом, творческая деятельность содействует сенсорному воспитанию развитию наглядно-образного мышления. Детское творчество имеет общественную направленность. Ребенок рисует, лепит, конструирует не только для себя, но и для окружающих. Ему хочется, чтобы его рисунок что-то выразал, чтобы изображенное им узнали.

Общественная направленность детского изобразительного творчества проявляется и в том, что в своей работе дети передают явления общественной жизни. Значение занятий творческой изобразительной деятельностью для нравственного воспитания заключается также в том, что в процессе этих занятий у детей воспитываются нравственно-волевые качества: потребность и умение доводить начатое до конца, сосредоточенно и целенаправленно заниматься, помогать товарищу, преодолевать трудности и т.п.

Творческая деятельность должна быть использована для воспитания у детей доброты, справедливости, для углубления тех благородных чувств, которые возникают в процессе творческой изобразительной деятельности сочетается умственная и физическая активность. Для создания рисунка, лепки, аппликации необходимо приложить усилия, осуществить трудовые действия, овладеть определенными умениями. Изобразительная деятельность дошкольников учит их преодолевать трудности, проявлять трудовые усилия, овладевать трудовыми навыками. Сначала у детей возникает интерес к

движению карандаша или кисти, к следам оставляемыми ими на бумаге; постепенно появляются новые мотивы творчества – желание получить результат, создать определенное изображение.

Дошкольники овладевают многими практическими навыками, которые позднее будут нужны для выполнения самых разнообразных работ, приобретают ручную умелость, которая позволит им чувствовать себя самостоятельными.

Освоение трудовых умений и навыков связано с развитием таких волевых качеств личности, как внимание, упорство, выдержка. У детей воспитываются умения трудиться, добиваться желаемого результата. Формированию трудолюбия, навыков самообслуживания способствует участие ребят в подготовке к занятиям и уборке рабочих мест.

Основное значение изобразительной деятельности заключается в том, что она является средством эстетического воспитания. Непосредственное эстетическое чувство, которое возникает при восприятии красивого предмета, включает различные составляющие элементы: чувство цвета, чувство пропорции, чувство формы, чувство ритма.

Для эстетического воспитания детей и для развития их творческих способностей большое значение имеет знакомство с произведениями и творческого искусства. Яркость, выразительность образов в картинках, скульптуре, архитектуре и произведениях прикладного искусства вызывают эстетические переживания, помогают глубже и полнее воспринимать явления жизни и находить образные выражения своих впечатлений в рисунке, лепке, аппликации. Постепенно у детей развивается художественный вкус.

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EFFECTIVE TECHNIQUES OF TEACHING VOCABULARY TO YOUNG LEARNERS.

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Shirinqulova Sitora Muzaffar qizi

Student of SamSIFL

Narzikulova Maftuna Salimovna

Teacher of SamSIFL

Abstract The article will discuss some effective ways of teaching vocabulary to young learners. Vocabulary is considered as the most essential part of a particular language. It is important to get acquainted with new words while learning languages. For this reason, some ways and techniques are recommended below which can be useful in teaching and learning process of vocabulary for the young generation.

Keywords: vocabulary, young learners, learning, teaching, language, teacher, communication, words, techniques.

Introduction

Children need to have a rich vocabulary that continually grows through language and literacy experiences, in order to comprehend and construct increasingly complex texts, and engage in oral language for a variety of social purposes. It's hard for students to read and understand a text if they don't know what the words mean. A solid vocabulary boosts reading comprehension for students of all ages. The more words students know, the better they understand the text. That's why effective vocabulary teaching is so important, especially for students who learn and think differently.

Main part

To improve and enrich our vocabularies there are some ways, for example by vocabulary. Name animal, media picture to get many words. Teachers have the important role to build children's vocabularies. They should know the factors in teaching such as methods, strategies, techniques, and materials, so that the teacher can convey the materials well in accordance with children's characteristics.

Learning vocabulary is a continual process of language and literacy development, which begins in the early years of life, and continues through schooling and beyond. Sinatra, Zygouris-Coe, and Dasinger note that:

Knowledge of vocabulary meanings affects children's abilities to understand and use words appropriately during the language acts of listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Such knowledge influences the complexities and nuances of children's thinking, how they communicate in the oral and written languages, and how well they will understand printed texts [1.333].

Young learners mean children from the first year of formal schooling (5 or 6 year old) to eleven or twelve year age. Young learners have own special characteristic that differentiate them from adult learners. It should be know and understood by the teacher to give contribution to improve their quality of teaching process (Halliwel, 1992). [3]

Techniques of Teaching Vocabulary:

There are three main stages in teaching vocabulary. In other word, there is some common techniques used in each stage as follow:

Techniques in Presenting. Yet it is the important stage that the student is introduced with the new words. As an English teacher, we should know the techniques of teaching vocabulary which are suitable for the students.

Techniques in Practicing. In practicing stage, there are a variety of tasks which can be used in order to help move words into long-term memory.

Media is a main instrument in teaching and learning process. It is used to attract the students' attention and deliver the information easily. Teachers of young learners have to use some visuals in their teaching activities to facilitate their teaching. According to Wright, there are various kinds of media, but visual is appropriate media for young learners in learning vocabulary.

Listen and Repeat technique was used by the teacher to introduce new vocabulary. In this technique the teacher asked the students to repeat after the words she read. The words were read slowly and repeatedly, so the students could follow

well. It was done continually and it made the students familiar with the new words [4].

In order to help young learners learn vocabulary effectively, we need to employ a range of strategies. First, we need to think why the young learner wants to know the words we teach as they are much more likely to remember them if they need them or want to use them. One way a teacher can do this is to get the learners to draw or write the words they already know and then draw or write the L1 translation of words they want to know. This can be followed by a spot of peer teaching where learners who know the second set of words teach them to the learners who want to know them. Another way to help young learners learn new words is to explore ways of recording vocabulary. Show learners some examples of picture dictionaries, words with sentences in English explaining what they mean and mind maps linking words and ideas. Discuss why these strategies are helpful. Encourage the learners to use these strategies when noting down new words.

It is crucial that children have explicit and robust instruction in vocabulary, to support their verbal and written communication. The explicit teaching of vocabulary allows students to access academic language and discourse, and facilitates their comprehension of increasingly complex texts [2].

Conclusion

If we want our young learners to be effective learners of vocabulary, we have to invest in teaching them strategies that help them to remember the words and produce them when they need them. Using the strategies above will help them develop their vocabulary and increase the total number of words they know.

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THE THREAT OF EXTREMISM TO NATIONAL SECURITY AND STABILITY

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Kurbanov Djamshid Djurayevich

*Head of the Department of UNI Academic Lyceum,
Independent Researcher of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute*

Annotation: This article presents the current experience in combating extremism, as well as a retrospective and comparative analysis of the situation in the countries of the region in combating these threats.

Keywords: globalization, extremism, civil servants, society, terrorism

In the current globalization and the ongoing transformation of international and regional conflicts, the issue of effective fight against extremism and terrorism remains one of the urgent topics on the agenda. At the same time, extremist and international terrorist organizations continue to spread violence and radical views in society by inciting youth to violence, to lose their national identity, cultural-educational and family values under the guise of religious beliefs. All this creates conditions for citizens to join the ranks of extremist and terrorist organizations. In this regard, determining more effective measures aimed at preventing and ending extremism and terrorism, as well as eliminating the sources and channels of their financing, as well as combining efforts at the national and international levels in this regard, are important directions of state policy.

According to the manifestation of religious extremism, it is divided into regional, regional and international forms. Such views have very ancient roots, religious extremism has never known borders, does not recognize nation, territory, and has developed within all religions. No matter where and under which religious banner religious extremists operate, their main ideological goal is to establish a religious state, and this goal is achieved through conflicts, armed conflicts, that is, bloodshed.

At a time when the struggle for the mind and soul of humanity has acquired a new qualitative character, it is important to emphasize the commonality of faith (for example, pan-Islamism), the emphasis on ethnic unity (for example, pan-Slavism), and the dependence caused by living in a single socio-economic and political space. It should be noted that there are attempts to ideologically divide the world space by ensuring the dominance of single ideologies on the basis of alienation (for example, Pan-Sovietism).

Today, it can be seen that the interests of extremist groups are manifested in the following:

- political goals aimed at changing the state administration, socio-economic system and internal policy;
- economic interests aimed at derailing the economy by acquiring strategically important properties, enterprises and structures of organizations and certain individuals;
- creating ethnic-national conflicts directed at representatives of certain nationalities and national groups against other nationalities and national groups living in the same territory;
- aimed at creating disorder among civil servants and goals aimed at eliminating the structures of society that use force;
- religious terrorism aimed at seizing power by some extremist groups under religious slogans;
- criminal terrorism aimed at discrediting the government, creating an atmosphere of fear and mistrust in the society through theft, robbery and invasion by invading groups consisting of various criminal elements.

The strategic goals of religious extremist terrorist organizations in Uzbekistan are the creation of a theocratic state based on Sharia, and for this purpose, the following is envisaged:

- “Islamization” of the population on a large scale;
- destabilization of social and political situation;

➤ intensifying inter-religious and inter-ethnic relations;

➤ establishing strong relations with religious-extremist organizations operating abroad, using their opportunities in training the group's fighters and providing material and technical support for their activities.

The main methods of activity of religious extremist organizations are as follows:

- distribution of leaflets, literature, video and audio tapes in a religious extremist spirit, including the ideas of “jihad”;
- inculcating radical Islamic concepts taught in secret “cells”;
- strong condemnation of the socio-political situation in Uzbekistan;
- discredit official religious structures;
- creation of secret groups and special training of its members;
- trying to include their supporters in state structures;
- strengthening cells consisting of women;
- effective use of terrorist means [1].

In conclusion, it is known that such religious extremist and terrorist organizations carry out their evil actions on the basis of plans and specific goals by creating a comprehensive, reliable cooperation with all terrorist structures and actions, mutual interest, both material and financial unity.

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TEMURIYZODA SHAHZODALARNING HINDISTON EGALLASH JARAYONIDAGI JASORATI XUSUSIDA

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BUXORO DAVLAT PEDAGOGIKA INSTITUTI

“Ijtimoiy fanlar kafedrasi” o‘qituvchisi Kenjayev Sardor Nurmurod o‘g‘li

Tarix ta’lim yo‘nalishi talabalari: Nematova Nigina, Xalilov Behruz,

Mardonova Feruza, Mirzayev Nusrat

Anotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Temuriyzoda shahzodalarning Hindiston egallash jarayonidagi jasorati xususida, Hindistonda fillar bilan olib borilgan janglarda shahzodalarning harbiy mahorati xususida fikr yuritilgan

Kalit so‘z: Hindiston, fillar, o‘rmon, Pir Muhammad, Ferushoh, Malluxon, Tog‘ayxon va Amir Ali, Bibi xonim, Yodgor Barlos, SHayx Nuriddinbek, Amir Mizrob Qamariy , Temur Hoja Oq Bug‘o, Xalil Sulton, Sulton Husayn, Jahonshohbek, Shayx Arslon

Bibi Xonim tarbiyasini olgan Xalil Sulton 10- 12 yoshlaridan boshlab harbiy ilmini o‘ryganishga, o‘zini chiniqtirishga intiladi. U bobosining bir qancha yuruyishlarida qatnashadi. 14 yoshida Hindistonga qilingan harbiy safar chog‘larida shahzoda bu ilmni qanchali ko‘zlashtirganligini amalda namoyish etadi . Hindiston podsholari, ayniqsa, Sulton Mahmud, uning nabirasi Feruzshoh, Malluxon, Tog‘ayxon va Amir Alilar Sohibqiron qo‘shinlariga qarshi son -san oqsiz sipohiy jamlab, qattiq qarshilik ko‘rsatadilar. O‘n ming otliq askar, qirqming piyoda, yuz yigirmafilga qarshi jang qilish Sohibqironning Pir Muhammad, Rustam, Sulaymonshohbek, Yodgor Barlos, SHayx Nuriddinbek, Amir Mizrob Qamariy , Temur Hoja Oq Bug‘o, Xalil Sulton, Sulton Husayn, Jahonshohbek, Shayx Arslon, Shayx Muhammad Iygu Temur, Sevinchak Bahodur kabi nabiralari va beklari zimmasiga tushgandi. Fillar, muarrix ta’kidlaganidek, yuruvchi tog‘lar monand bo‘lib, sovut bilan qoplangan, ustida yog‘ochdan ravoq qilinib, unda besh -oltita kamonchi -tirandoz o‘tirardi . Fillardagi vajohat uni avval ko‘rmagan Sohibqiron sipohlarning bir qismini vahimaga solib qo‘yadi. Sharafiddin Ali Yazdiy shu o‘rinda bir qochirim

keltiradi . Uning Amir Temur hazratlari doimo yurishlarda o‘zi bilan birga donish - mandlarni , olim va allomalarni birga olib yurgan. Hindiston yurishida ham Hoja Fazl, shayxulislom Sa‘d Jalolal -haqvad -din Kashshiy (Keshiy), Mavlono Abduljabbor va Mavlono Numonad -din Xorazmiy singari kishilar hamsafar bo‘lganlar.

Sohibqiron fillar qarshisida qo‘rquvga tushib qolgan bu zotlarga bir hazil qilgisi va, ayni vaqtda, ularning ruhini kutargisi kelib, «Sizlar qayerda turishni istaysizlar», deb so‘raydi. Fillar dahshatidan titrab qaqshayotgan ulamolarning tillari zo‘rg‘a kalimaga kelib, «b-b-bizning j -j -joyimiz xo-xotinlar o-orasida», deydilar. Sohibqiron bu gapni eshitib, xoxolab kulib yuboradi. Birgina shu kulgining uzi nafaqat shayxuolimlarniig shu bilan birga ichki titroqda bo‘lgan ayrim beklarning, sipohlarning ham ko‘nglini ko‘tarib, qo‘rquv vahmini chilparchin qilib yuboradi. Jang boshlanadi, shahzoda Pir Muhammad Mirzo birinchi bo‘lib filga qilich bilan zarba beradi. Dushmanning ko‘l qismida turgan sipohlar jangovar fillarni maydonga soladilar. Amir Temur bahodirlari kamondan o‘q otib fillarni yaralashga , shamshir bilan xartumlarini kesishga erishadilar. Muarrix, Hind bahodirlarining botiliklari to‘g‘risida ham yozishni unutmaydi. Fil jangida Xalil Sulton, ayniqsa, mardlik namunasini ko‘rsatadi. U filbonni qilich solib o‘ldirib, filni «xuddi sigirni haydagandek», Sohibqiron oldiga olib keladi. «Zafarnoma»ni mutolaa qilishda e‘tibordan chetda qolib kelgan ayrim chizgilar qayta mushohadaga bois bo‘lmay qolmaydi. Sohibqiron davlat tuzumida boshqaruv nihoyatda aniq darajada yo‘lga qo‘yilganligi mulklarni idora qilayotgan shahzodalar haqida vaqti -vaqti bilan xabarlar etkazilib turilishida ham ko‘rinadi . Hindiston fathi davom etayotgan kezlarda ham Tabrizdan , Fors o‘lkalaridan xabarchilar kelib, Amironshoh va Pir Muhammad Umarshayx Mirzolarining ahvoli, sog‘lig‘i, yurtining tinchligi to‘g‘risida o‘ziga xos «hisobotlar» olib keladi.

1399 yilning 3 martida Sohibqiron qo‘shini Chinob daryosini kechib o‘tganida Tabrizdan Amironsh Mirzoning navkarlari etib keladilar va Bardoy, Misr,

SHom, Rum, Dashti Qipchoq va Alanchiq qal'asi haqida to'liq ma'lumot beradilar, shahzodaning sog'lig'i to'g'risda ham so'zlaydilar.

Sohibqiron Hindistondan qaytgandan so'ng, Xonzoda Beginning Samarqandga kelishi, Amironshoh Mirzo ustidan arz va etti yillik yurishning boshlani voqealari sodir bo'ladi. Xalil Sulton bu paytda 16 yoshga to'lgan baxtli shahzoda edi⁷.

Shohruh Mirzo Xurosonga hukmdor bo'lganida 20 yoshga to'lgan edi. Buvaqtda uing Ulug'bek, Ibroxim Sulton va Boysungur Mirzo ismli uch o'g'li bor edi. Xurosonda boshqaruvni yo'lga ko'yib, ancha tajriba orttirgan SHohruh Mirzo Sohobqironning Hindiston yurishiga o'z lashkari bilan jalb etiladi. Hindiston safari hijriy 800 yilningr ajab oyida (mart - aprel. 1398) boshlanadp. Amir Temur hazratlari Andarabga kelib tushganida shuyurtning kattadan - kichigi uning oldiga kelib, jangari va yarim yovvoyi Qatur va Siyohpo'sh lardan himoya qilishni arzga etkazadilar. Arz qiluvchilar, «Biz musulmonlar jamoasimiz, busrlarni vatan tutganmiz.

Shohruh Mirzo Hirotda, o'z mulklarini boshqarish uchun qaytarib jo'natilgani bilan, uning lashkaridan kerakli qismi Hindiston fathi uchun qoldirilgan. Batnir qal'asini zabt etishda SHohruh Mirzoning Sulaymonshohbek, Sayyid Hoja va Jahon Malik singari amirlari faol qatnashganlar. Hindistonga qilingan yurish muvaffaqiyatli yakun topadi. G'alaba yor bo'lgach, Sohobqiron Movarozchsh ahrga qayta boshaydi. Hindiston yurishi zafari bo'layotgan edi.

Nima sababdan bu ish oxiriga yetkazilmaganligi sabablarli noma'lumligicha qolib kelmoqda. Ibn Arabshoh, o'zicha bu qaytishni Amironshoh Mirzoning «Xatiga» bog'laydi. Ibn Arabshoh to'qimasi gang puch va asossiz ekanligini 1399 y ilning 3 martida Tabrizdan Amir Temur huzuriga Amironshoh Mirzoning odamlari kelganligi, shahzodaning sog'lig'i va ishlari yaxshishi ekanligi xabarini etkazishi

⁷ Равшанов, Поён Амир Темур сулоласи: роман. / П.Равшанов. -Тошкент: Янги аср авлоди, 2014. - 309 б

dalili ochiq-oydin ko‘rsatadi . Ashraf Ahmedov, shu haqda mulohaza qilgan ekan , Amironshoh odyamlari, «agar Ibn Arabshoh aytgan xatni keltirganlarida edi Amir Temur Hindistondan qaytishni besh kunga ham kechiktirmas edi», degan hulosaga keladi. Muarrix Yazdiyning guvohlik berishicha, Sohibqiron Amir Temur 1399 yilning 8 martida (Mironshoh xuzuridan odamlar kelganidan besh kun keyin) Samarqandga tomon otlanadi . Ashraf Ahmyedov to‘g‘ri uqdirganidek , amalda shunday xat bo‘lganida edi, Amir Temur qaytishni bir lahza bo‘lsin paysalga solmagan bo‘lardi. Sohibqironning shoshilmaslan qaytishi , hatto yo‘l bo‘yi qurilish , bunyodkorlik ishlari bilan mashg‘ul bo‘lishi uning ko‘ngli hotirjamligidan , hech bir narsa bezovta qilmayotganidan darak beradi. 12 mart kuni Sohibqiron agar qal’asini ko‘rishga boradi. Ertasiga, 13 martda Amironshoh Mirzo oldidan kelgan odamlarga Tabrizga, o‘g‘li yoniga qaytishga ijozat beradi. Sohibqiron Hindistonga yurish boshlaganida Sulaymon shohbekka Nagar qal’asini qayta boshdan kurish topshirig‘i ni bergan edi. Qal’a qurilishi davomida uning devorlari tashqarisida zilol suvli buloq borligi aniqlanadi. Amir Temur qal’ani ko‘zdan kechi rayotganida, shu buloqning qal’a ichida bo‘lishi juda xohlaydi. Muarrix, «Sohibqiron bola-chaqalarini sog‘ingan bo‘lsa-da, shu fikrini amalga oshirish uchun otdan tushib, shu erda qoladi», deydi. Qal’a devorlari kengaytiriladi, bu shunchalik jadal olib boriladiki, hatto beklarning o‘zlari ham g‘isht tashishga kirishib ketadilar.

Uch kun ichida devor qayta tiklanib, zilol suvli buloq qal’aning ichkarisiga olinadi. Sohibqiron bu xayrli ishni amalga oshirganidan keyin, yo‘lnidavom ettiradi. 18 mart kuni Aramak Daxana degan mavzega kelib tushganida, Mavlono Ne’matni Hirotdan, SHohruh Mirzo huzuriga jo‘natadi . Kobulga etib kelib, o‘zi barpo qildirgan Navanohi tegrasida to‘xtaydi. Oradan ikki kun o‘tib, Nahushak manzalga etishilganida, Amir Temur hazratlarining qo‘l va oyoqlarida chidab bo‘lmas og‘riq boshlanadi. Bu, 1362 yilda olgan jarohatlar asoratidan edi. Hindistonga borishda to‘rt ming metrlik tog‘lardan oshib o‘tish , sovuq va qorda yurish endi o‘z ta’siri ni ko‘rsatayotgan edi. SHu kuni, 20 martda Hirotdan, SHohruh Mirzo oldidan xos kishilar kelishadi va shahzodaning sog‘lig‘i, ishlari to‘g‘risida ma’lumot beradilar.

Qo‘l va oyoq og‘rig‘i shuqadar zo‘rayadiki , otlanish , yo‘lni davom ettirish imkoni bo‘lmaydi. Yaxshiyamki , 23 martda Sohibqiron oldiga Saroy Mulk Xonim, Tuman Og‘o va boshqa malikalar, nabira shaxdodalar etib kelishadi. Amir Temurning xastaligi hammaning ko‘nglini cho‘ktirib yuborgan, hech kimning chiroyi ochilmasdi. Oilaviy muhit, yaqinlar diydori tafti sabab, 25 martda og‘riq chekinadi , Sohibqiron qurshovida shodmonlik qaror topadi . Sohibqironning Hindistondan muzaffar qayti - shi juda katta xushnudliklarga sabab bo‘ladi. Jayhundan o‘tishda Sohibqiron shahzodalar, malikalar, ulug‘ zotlar tomonidan shodu xurramlik bilan qarshi olinadi. SHunchalik ko‘p sochqilar sochiladiki , Amu qirg‘oqlari oltin va kumush bilan qoplandi, deb yozadi muarrix Sohibqiron, odati bo‘yicha, Termiz va Keshda ziyoratgohlarga boradi, ulug‘ avliyolar, otasi va avlodlariga -ehsonlar tarqatadi.

1399 yilning 27 aprel kuni Samarqandga etib keladi va Dilkusho bog‘iga tushadi . Ertasiga Qusam ibn Abbos marqadini ziyorat qiladi , yig‘ilgan xaloyiqqa ehsonlar ulash adi. SHunda Samarqand aholisi Hindistondan olib kelingan fillarni birinchi bor ko‘rib, hayratdan yoqa ush - laydi . Qaytish tan tanalari nihoyasiga etgach, Jayhundan poytaxtga qadar otasiga hamrohlik qilib kelgan SHohruh Mirzo Hirotga jo‘nashga izn so‘raydi. Hindiston safaridan keyin , etarli halovat olmasdan burun, yuz bergan noxush voqealarni o‘quvchi oldingi qism hikoyalaridan yaxshi biladi. Eronga qilinadigan etti yillik yurish mudatidan ancha oldin - Xonzoda Begim arzi -shikoyati sabab, boshlanib ketadi.

Sohibqironning Hindiston yurishida Hoja Fazl, shayxulislom Sa‘d Jaloliddin Keshiy, Mavlono Abdujabbor va Mavlono Nu‘moniddin Xorazmiy kabi taniqli olimlar, ula olar hamrohlik kalgan - lar. Bu olimlarniyng ishi sipohiyalar qalbiga Laxoh ishonchinp mahkam o‘rnashtirish bidan bir qatorda, shahzodalarga ta‘lim berish bilan ham bog‘liq bo‘lgan, deyish utlaqo o‘rinlidir.

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ИНТЕРЕС К САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНЫМ ЗАНЯТИЯМ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРОЙ СТУДЕНТОВ

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Кокандский государственный педагогический институт

Преподаватель Преподаватель кафедры методики физической культуры

Иномов Фахриддин Ёрмонович

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается проблема повышения уровня заинтересованности студентов высших учебных заведений путем организации самостоятельных занятий физической культурой.

Ключевые слова: физическая культура, самостоятельные занятия, студенты.

Физическая культура студентов выступает качественной и результативной мерой комплексного воздействия разнообразных форм, средств, методов на личность будущего специалиста в процессе формирования его профессиональной компетенции, а результатом этого процесса является уровень индивидуальной физической культуры студента, его духовность, уровень развития и подготовленности к профессиональной жизнедеятельности.

Давно известно, теоретически доказано и подтверждено практикой: отсутствие оптимальной двигательной активности является препятствием в освоении учебного материала. Экономия на физическом воспитании учащейся молодежи, человечество не только наносит ущерб здоровью этих молодых людей, но и лишает их полноценного умственного, аналитического и в целом интеллектуального развития.

Сегодня, начиная со студентов первого курса университета, наблюдается рост числа обучающихся, имеющих подготовительную (слабое физическое развитие) и специальную (патологические отклонения в состоянии здоровья) медицинские группы. При этом число студентов специальной медицинской группы в отдельных регионах страны превышает 60 процентов.

В тех высших учебных заведениях, где физическое воспитание студентов поставлено на должный уровень, где широкий охват имеет физкультурно-

массовая и спортивная работа вне сетки учебного расписания, где практикуются и контролируются в дополнение к аудиторной физической нагрузке самостоятельные занятия, подавляющая часть студентов подготовительной и специальной медицинских групп успешно реабилитируются и переходят в группу практически здоровых людей.

Внедрение физической культуры и спорта в повседневную жизнь каждого

студента, как того требуют физиологические законы развивающегося организма

прямой путь не только к повышению уровня здоровья студентов, но и в целом к оздоровлению нации и в психофизическом, и в социально-экономическом плане. Нами было проведено исследование среди студентов первого и третьего

курсов, целью которого являлось определение числа студентов, занимающихся самостоятельно физическими упражнениями.

Все пункты анкеты направлены на выявление отношения студентов к здоровому образу жизни и к самостоятельным (дополнительным) занятиям физической культурой. Для обработки данных анкетирования использован метод контент-анализа.

Сравнительный анализ представляет собой метод анализа объектов, при котором производится сравнение нового состояния объекта со старым состоянием или сравнение состояния одного объекта с другим, с которым сравнение может быть уместным. Сравнительный анализ является одним из основных методов.

1) 11 из 15 первокурсников регулярно посещают занятия физкультурой, в то время как из 13 студентов третьего курса занятия по физической культуре

посещают 5 человек. Возможно, это связано с тем, что студенты к третьему курсу становятся более вольными в посещении занятий, некоторые находят работу и считают, что можно пропустить несколько пар. Также у них появляются курсовые работы, их студенческая жизнь более насыщенная, поэтому третьекурсники относятся к занятиям физической культурой несерьезно, отодвигая их на второй план.

2) Спортивным человеком себя считают 10 опрошенных первокурсников из 15, 7 из 10 иногда посещают бассейн, тренажерный зал и т.д. Еще два человека из 10 регулярно занимаются спортом, а третий старается уделять спорту все свое свободное время. Остальные 5 из опрошенных считают, что они далеко не спортивные люди. У студентов третьего курса результат немного иной. Спортивными себя считают 8 человек из 15. Из них 4 студента иногда посещают тренажерный зал, и еще 4 стараются посещать его регулярно. Остальные опрошенные не считают себя спортивными.

3) Из общего числа опрошенных студентов только 11 из 30 делают зарядку по утрам (из них 7 первокурсников и 4 третьекурсника). Можно связать это с нарушением режима, как известно, студенты поздно ложатся спать, и многие из них рано встают. Возможно, опрошенные не делают зарядку из-за нехватки времени, но нельзя исключать и безответственность, ведь большая часть из них осведомлена, что даже недолгая утренняя зарядка поможет взбодриться утром и чувствовать себя лучше, но студенты не считают это важной частью своей жизни.

4) Для 24 опрошенных студентов здоровый образ жизни подразумевает отказ от курения и алкоголя, а также занятия физическими упражнениями. И только для оставшихся 6 человек здоровый образ жизни – это лишь отсутствие вредных привычек. Нужно отметить, что никто из опрошенных не считает, что здоровый образ жизни включает в себя вредные привычки.

5) На вопрос ведете ли вы здоровый образ жизни 4 из 15 первокурсников и 6 из 15 третьекурсников ответили, что да. Можно сделать вывод, что

остальные опрошенные пренебрегают не только самостоятельными физическими упражнениями, но и теми, что предусмотрены на практических занятиях по физической культуре в университете. Также ни для кого не секрет, что сейчас большая часть молодого поколения злоупотребляет алкоголем и с раннего возраста начинает курить. Из-за этого подобный образ жизни также нельзя назвать здоровым, даже если эти студенты занимаются физическими упражнениями.

Если сравнивать ответы студентов первого и третьего курса в целом, то можно сделать вывод, что третьекурсники реже посещают занятия по физической культуре в университете, зато из их числа больше людей, которые чаще посещают спортзал, следовательно, занимаются самостоятельными физическими упражнениями, что, возможно, более эффективно. Зато среди них меньше тех, кто делает зарядку утром.

Отношение молодежи к спорту и физическим упражнениям оставляет желать лучшего, к сожалению, для многих опрошенных это совсем неважная часть жизни. Из анкетирования стало ясно, что из 24 студентов лишь 19 занимаются физическими упражнениями дополнительно, то есть самостоятельно, посещая тренажерный зал или бассейн. Это больше половины, но если учитывать возраст опрашиваемых студентов, результат должен быть лучше, ведь именно в таком молодом возрасте нужно уделять своему организму особое внимание, чтобы в будущем предотвратить многие болезни и недуги.

Посещать занятия физической культурой в университете важно и необходимо, особенно если студент дополнительно не занимается спортом. Ведь в жизни должна присутствовать хотя бы минимальная физическая активность. Но, даже несмотря на то, что многие студенты занимаются самостоятельно, это не дает им права пропускать занятия физкультурой, ведь чем больше дней, когда человек занимается, тем лучше. Например, самостоятельно можно заниматься в иные дни, тем самым установить баланс:

допустим, в университете занятия по понедельникам и четвергам, а самостоятельные – по вторникам и пятницам, или же по средам и субботам. Также нельзя исключать каждодневную утреннюю зарядку: как уже было упомянуто ранее, это способствует лучшему пробуждению.

Благодаря этому организм способен адекватно реагировать на внешние физические и психические раздражители, в конечном итоге люди, которые выполняют утреннюю зарядку, меньше испытывают стресс. Но согласно результатам анкетирования, совсем малая часть опрошенных студентов делают зарядку. Многие студенты понимают всю важность самостоятельных физических упражнений и уделяют этому определенное время. Но немалая часть вообще не занимается ими, из-за этого они быстро утомляются, не обладают достаточной выносливостью.

И это, на самом деле, большая проблема. Для ее решения, можно проводить в университетах лекции, на которых студентам расскажут о важности физических упражнений, особенно самостоятельных (дополнительных). Ведь если сейчас не заниматься спортом или хотя бы минимальными физическими упражнениями, то в будущем здоровье может уже не позволить это делать.

Физическая культура и спорт – средства созидания гармонично развитой личности. Они помогают сосредоточить все внутренние ресурсы организма на достижение поставленной цели, повышают работоспособность, позволяют втиснуть в рамки короткого дня выполнение всех намеченных дел, вырабатывают потребность в здоровом образе жизни. Сегодня нужно совершенствовать традиционные и применять новые формы и методы проведения массовой оздоровительной, физкультурной и спортивной работы.

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ЛЕГКАЯ АТЛЕТИКА КАК ВИД ЭЛЕКТИВНЫХ КУРСОВ ПО ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЕ И СПОРТА

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Кокандский государственный педагогический институт

Старший преподаватель кафедры методики физической культуры

Ирматов Шавкат Анварович

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются вопросы, связанные с реализацией элективных курсов по физической культуре и спорту на примере преподавания легкой атлетики на базе

Ключевые слова: физическая культура, спорт, здоровье, легкая атлетика.

Физическое воспитание в учебных заведениях призвано укреплять здоровье, способствовать нормальному физическому развитию. На занятиях физической культурой учащиеся получают важные навыки в двигательной деятельности – в беге, ходьбе, метании предмета и так далее. К сожалению, отмечается тенденция растущего пассивного отношения студентов к практическим занятиям по физической культуре, что вызывает необходимость искать новые формы приобщения молодежи к двигательной активности, поскольку наблюдается отрицательная динамика в состоянии здоровья и показателей физической подготовленности студентов начальных курсов.

В связи с этим возникает необходимость поиска путей актуализации образовательного процесса по физической культуре в соответствии с учебными планами высшего учебного заведения. Наиболее оптимальным способом, который должен повысить интерес к учебным занятиям по дисциплине «Физическая культура» является спортивно-ориентированное физическое воспитание в форме элективных курсов, так как они основаны на учете интересов, обучающихся к конкретным видам спорта с учетом их индивидуальных особенностей.

Легкая атлетика как один из основных и наиболее массовых видов спорта, способна развивать все эти виды физических упражнений. В нашей стране легкая атлетика составляет основную часть программы всех образовательных учреждений. И это вовсе не случайно, так как эти упражнения развивают организм наиболее равномерно и гармонично. Системы легкоатлетических упражнений имеют оздоровительный эффект для всего организма в целом.

Помимо мышечной активности они развивают сердечно-сосудистую систему, дыхание, вестибулярный аппарат, реакцию. Занятия легкой атлетики воспитывает командный дух, чувство коллективизма. В дальнейшей жизни навыки, полученные на занятиях по легкой атлетике, пригодятся в трудовой деятельности, в армейской жизни. Именно занятия по легкой атлетике в рамках реализации комплекса ГТО в своё время сыграли положительную роль.

Лёгкая атлетика – олимпийский вид спорта, который включает в себя бег, ходьбу, прыжки и метания. Она относится к числу популярных видов спорта, так как не требует специальных условий для занятий. Основные физические качества, которые развивает лёгкая атлетика – это выносливость, сила, скорость, гибкость. Занятия лёгкой атлетикой помогают приобрести двигательные навыки ходьбы, бега, прыжков, преодоления препятствий, которые необходимы в повседневной жизни. Так же приобретаются навыки координации движений, быстрого перемещения и рационального выполнения сложных физических упражнений.

Сначала следует подготовительный этап непосредственно до тренировки. Растяжка мышц является неотъемлемой частью занятий, но только в том случае, если предварительно разогрето тело, например, ненавязчивым бегом в течение 15-20 минут. Для этих целей применяются специальные беговые упражнения: семенящий бег с носка на пятку; семенящий бег с пятки на носок; бег с высоким подниманием бедра; много со сменой ног (прыжки с одной ноги на другую с акцентом на длину, которые призваны для разминки четырехглавой бедренной и трехглавой голенистой мышцы); ускорение.

Следует обратить внимание на то, что любые статические упражнения до делать как можно больше упражнений в динамике для того, чтобы разогнать кровь. Далее следуют разминочные упражнения: круговые движения головой в правую и левую стороны; рывки руками (вверх/вниз): правая рука вверху левая внизу, на 1-2 рывки руками, на 3-4 осуществляется смена рук; круговые движения в плечевом, локтевом и лучезапястном суставах; наклоны туловища в стороны; круговые движения в тазобедренном суставе; перенос веса тела с одной ноги на другую.

Присед на одной ноге, другая в сторону, на 1 пережат в одну сторону на 2 в другую. Выпады вперед с одной ноги на другую. Присед на опорной ноге, маховая назад в прямом положении. На 1-2 пружинистые движения, 3-4 смена ног. Произвольные круговые движения в коленном и голеностопном суставах. Отметим, что именно легкая атлетика позволяет максимально привлечь студентов к занятиям спорту в отличие от игровых видов: не требуется в большинстве видов специального оборудования, предварительной подготовки, специфических данных (рост, координация, сила подачи).

Наиболее популярными среди студентов занимающихся легкой атлетикой, являются беговые тренировки. Среди основных видов бега можно выделить следующие: короткие, средние и длинные дистанции, бег с какими-либо барьерами или препятствиями, эстафетный бег. Классическими дистанциями в беге на короткие дистанции являются: бег на 100, 200 и 400 метров. Основные дистанции в беге на средние дистанции: 800, 1500 и 3000 метров (с препятствиями).

Дистанции от 3000 метров принято называть длинными (или стайерские). Студенты, состоящие в легкоатлетической команде филиала, участвуют в таких ежегодных соревнованиях.

В заключение отметим, что комплексные занятия по легкой атлетике в рамках элективных курсов по физической культуре и спорту являются одним из «механизмов» реализации целей и задач по профилактике заболеваний и

вредных привычек, а также укрепляют здоровье, поддерживают высокую работоспособность человека, формируют потребность личности в физическом и нравственном совершенствовании, развитии волевых качеств личности.

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РАЗВИТИЕ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ НА ЗАНЯТИИ ПО ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЕ

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*Кокандский государственный педагогический институт
Преподаватель кафедры «Спортивные и подвижные игры»*

Шокиров Шухрат Гайратович

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются особенности ценностных ориентаций студентов на физическую активность, физическое самосовершенствование и здоровый образ жизни, представлена оптимизация социально-педагогических условий для организации непрерывного физкультурного образования молодежи, расширения возможностей развития физической активности в соответствии с потребностями учащихся.

Ключевые слова: студенты, формирование, двигательная активность, здоровый образ жизни, физкультурное образование, этапы.

Всемирно признан факт полезности занятий физическими упражнениями и оздоровительными видами спорта – превентивным средством поддержания и укрепления здоровья, способствующим снижению риска неинфекционных заболеваний (сердечно-сосудистых, ишемической болезни сердца, диабета, остеопороза, ожирения и т. д.), а также эффективным средством профилактики девиантного поведения, распространения таких явлений, как алкоголизм, курение, наркомания.

Постоянное пристальное внимание к здоровому образу жизни студента связано с озабоченностью общества по поводу здоровья специалистов, выпускаемых высшей школой, роста заболеваемости в процессе профессиональной подготовки, последующего снижения работоспособности. Необходимо отчетливо понимать, что не существует здорового образа жизни как некой особенной формы жизнедеятельности вне образа жизни в целом. Различные государственные социальные программы, направленные на физкультурное образование студентов, ставят перед собой следующие

цели: обеспечение всестороннего гармоничного развития личности; сохранение и укрепление здоровья; формирование потребности в здоровом образе жизни и регулярной физической активности; освоение системы физкультурно-спортивных знаний, грамотности и компетентности в сфере физической культуры как части общей культуры личности; воспитание двигательных умений и навыков, способностей использовать полученные знания в дальнейшей жизнедеятельности.

Исследования специалистов направлены, в первую очередь, на формирование ценностных ориентаций студентов на физическую активность, физическое самосовершенствование и здоровый образ жизни, а также на оптимизацию социально-педагогических условий для организации непрерывного физкультурного образования молодежи, расширения возможностей для развития традиционных и нетрадиционных видов физической активности в соответствии с потребностями учащихся.

В основе формирования физической активности студентов лежат потребностно-мотивированные процессы, позволяющие индивиду не только достичь поставленных целей физического совершенствования, но и укрепить психическое и физическое здоровье, а также способствующие достижению социального благополучия и улучшения эмоционального состояния.

Дозированная мышечная нагрузка способствует разрядке отрицательных эмоций, снимает нервное напряжение и усталость, повышает жизненный тонус и работоспособность. Кроме того, импульсы, поступающие с работающих скелетных мышц, стимулируют течение восстановительных процессов, функциональную активность различных органов и систем.

Это имеет важное значение для сохранения здоровья, увеличения продолжительности жизни и повышения устойчивости организма к неблагоприятным факторам внешней среды. Систематическая двигательная активность улучшает функциональное состояние сердца и легких, расширяет артериальные кровеносные сосуды, обогащает организм человека

кислородом, успокаивает возбужденную нервную систему, дает положительный эмоциональный стимул.

Один из обязательных факторов здорового образа жизни студентов – систематические, соответствующие полу, возрасту, состоянию здоровья физические нагрузки. Они представляют собой сочетание разнообразных двигательных действий, выполняемых в повседневной жизни, в организованных и самостоятельных занятиях физическими упражнениями и спортом, объединенных термином «двигательная активность».

Спорт и физическая культура – это не только здоровый образ жизни, это вообще нормальная и здоровая жизнь, которая открывает все новые и новые возможности для реализации своих сил и талантов. Это путь, на который вступает здравомыслящий человек, для того чтобы прожитая им жизнь была плодотворной, приносила радость ему самому и окружающим.

Приобретение студентами физкультурно-спортивных знаний следует рассматривать как средство сделать свою физическую активность более эффективной. Затем она обособляется в особую сферу деятельности, а занятия физическими упражнениями начинают служить не целью, а средством приобретения знаний. Задача физкультурного образования в том и заключается, чтобы, трансформируя свое отношение к социальной ценности физической культуры на уровне человеческой культуры, повлиять на формирование позиции студентов.

Понимание социально-биологического наследования оздоровительных эффектов физической культуры имеет для переориентации общественного сознания в области физической культуры особое значение, позволяя рассматривать воздействие занятий физическими упражнениями на организм не как временное, преходящее явление, а как крупномасштабное и длительное, благотворными результатами которого пользуется не только занимающийся, но и его дети, потомство.

С целью формирования престижного имиджа спортивного стиля жизни, ценности собственного здоровья необходимо убедительно рассказывать молодежи о том, для чего следует заниматься физической культурой и спортом, в чем их ценность и какое значение они имеют для каждого человека в отдельности и для общества в целом, какова взаимосвязь между физической активностью людей и решением социально-экономических проблем, здоровым образом жизни, личным благополучием. Нужно разъяснять студентам, что такое двигательный режим, какое место он занимает в жизни каждого, каким он должен быть и как добиться его выполнения. Следует постоянно рассказывать о положительном опыте (личном, семейном, коллективном) организации занятий физической культурой с использованием научно обоснованных проверенных систем закаливания, питания, дыхания и т. д. с обязательным комментарием специалистов.

Известно, что занятия физическими упражнениями и спортом оказывают положительное влияние на физическое, психическое и социальное здоровье человека и имеют важнейшее значение на протяжении всей его жизни – с раннего детства до глубокой старости. Студентов необходимо обучать тому, чтобы они понимали, что физическая активность способствует улучшению настроения, хорошему самочувствию, снимает тревогу, усталость, депрессию и психосоциальный стресс, а также может стимулировать познавательные процессы.

Подготовка студента к активной самостоятельной жизнедеятельности осуществляется через его активные общественные действия, сознательное преобразование себя и окружающего мира в процессе целенаправленной деятельности и в условиях физической активности, в частности, через отношение к физической культуре (физкультурно-спортивные знания, умения и навыки, а также потребности, мотивы и интересы, регулярные занятия физическими упражнениями на занятиях и в режиме свободного времени).

Эффективность деятельности по формированию у молодежи позитивного отношения к регулярным занятиям физическими упражнениями также зависит от правильного взаимодействия педагогической системы и социальной инфраструктуры, научного обоснования новых подходов к повышению эффективности физического образования студентов, разработки базовых и вариативных учебных программ физического воспитания.

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**CONSIDERATION OF PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS IN THE
METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH IN THE STUDENTS STUDYING
GUIDE GUIDE AND TRANSLATION ACTIVITY AND THE
ACHIEVEMENTS ACHIEVED IN THIS FIELD.**

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Usmanova Sayyora Norimkulovna

Teacher of the Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

ABSTRACT This article describe the role of the guide in the "organization of the tour service", its qualities, the specifics of the profession of guide and what features it should have.

Keywords: Guide accompaniment, excursionist, communicability, organization, constructiveness, oratory, external speech, internal speech.

INTRODUCTION

Today, in our country, great importance is attached to the rapid development of the tourism sector, and in the medium-term perspective, the implementation of the domestic tourism development program "Travel through the territories of the Republic" has been set. The fulfillment of these tasks requires the further development of tourism and excursion services in Uzbekistan. Tourism excursion service is one of the main services in the field of tourism. Any tourist who visits first of all wants to get acquainted with the country's history, culture, social life, and natural resources. has an effect.

METHODOLOGY

The tasks facing the tour service can be shown as follows;

Guiding was not considered a profession until recently, it was just a fun activity for a group of amateurs. The work of the guide was carried out by specialists of various fields without separating from their main activities (pedagogues, scientific staff of the museum, scientific staff of the institute, etc.). Only a few sightseeing

establishments and individual museums had guides in the state. But at that time, this activity began to have professional characteristics."

The change in the function of the excursion service, its transformation from the form of recreation to the organizational form of cultural and educational work in labor communities, to the network serving the population, led to the rise of a new specialty, that is, the role of a guide.

Article 3 of the Law on Tourism of the Republic of Uzbekistan includes the concepts of tourist group leader (tour leader) and guide (excursion leader). A person acting on his behalf and ensuring the fulfillment of the terms of the tourist service contract ", "Guide (ekakursuya leader) - provides excursion-informational, organizational services and qualified assistance to tour participants within the framework of the tourist services contract. Definitions of "indicating natural person" are included.

It is necessary for every guide to know not only the knowledge of his specialty, but also the basics of pedagogy and psychology. It is necessary to be demanding.

The guide's communication with the excursionists, his recommendations and instructions have an educational effect. The information being studied enriches their consciousness spiritually and aesthetically. In, educates, forms a worldview. As in all pedagogical processes, two parties are involved in the excursion service: the teacher-guide and the student excursionist. The guide gives knowledge on a certain topic, and the excursionists receive it. The interaction between these two parties is the basis of the pedagogical process. In interaction with the tourists, the guide uses methods of pedagogical influence.

Pedagogical skills and pedagogical art form part of the professional qualification of a guide. Pedagogical skills of the guide include the following: - sufficient knowledge of the specialty; - ability to analyze, imaginative thinking; - understanding the psyche of the excursionist; - being able to manage a group; - to acquire knowledge and skills in the field of pedagogical techniques; - intuition; - respecting the tourist's personality.

The profession of a guide requires specific practical skills. This qualification gives him the ability to correctly select, embody and effectively transfer his knowledge to the audience.

DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS

During the excursion, the guide should ensure that the excursionists think together, analyze, sympathize, unite according to their interests and become a team. The guide should pay attention not only to educational, but also educational aspects of the excursion service. He should choose and use excursion information in such a way that excursionists develop such qualities as love for the homeland, respect for other nations, and their traditions.

In addition to choosing and providing complete and accurate information about the objects, the guide must also have personal qualities and professional skills. Ethical requirements imposed on a person are compliance with general principles and moral norms, striving for perfection. The formation of a person to be perfect and perfect in all aspects takes place during his whole life (in a general education school, college, higher education institution, in the community , in everyday life, in training courses for guides, in interaction with excursionists).

The main activity of the guide is to prepare and conduct the excursion service [5].

Preparation of excursion service is divided into 3 parts:

- 1) Preparation of individual text;
- 2) Remembering the requirements of methodical development;
- 3) Remembering the route.

The guide must develop and improve the following 4 types of abilities in order to be able to attract the tourists during the excursion, to maintain a stable group atmosphere:

- Constructivity;
- Organization;
- Communicativeness;

-Analysis.

Constructive ability is expressed in the ability to correctly select and formalize the information of the excursion service for the tourists, to convey it in an understandable and reliable way, to revise the excursion plan and the method of using methodological guides in necessary cases, and the guide's thinking is the basis of ability.

Organizational ability is reflected in the ability to manage the excursion group, direct their attention to the desired object, and perform services in the approved program for tourists and excursionists.

Communicative ability to establish a warm relationship when working with the excursion group, to maintain this atmosphere during the excursion service, to be able to absorb the characteristic of the culture of behavior and during the route, the bus driver, exhibition, museum workers, heads of methodological circles, is manifested in the process of establishing a proper relationship with other guides, leaders of tourist groups.

The ability to analyze is manifested in a critical analysis of one's work, an objective assessment of the quality of the excursion service, and the effectiveness of the application of methodological methods.

The role of the guide's temperament is important in the organization of the excursion service. Manifestation of human temperament (sanguine, choleric, melancholic, phlegmatic) is the result of general human culture. The guide's character, world view, free thinking, relationship established with the team qualitatively determines how the tour will go. The guide should know the norm in showing his inner and outer feelings and attitudes to the tourists.

"The guide's emotions, mood (extremely high or depressed) arising under the influence of external and internal disturbances should not affect the excursion process, self-control, providing the necessary environment in the group is the skill of the guide. the guide's feelings must have an objective character."

Each person has his own characteristics (speech, conveyance of information, gestures) that distinguish him from others. The guide should have the ability to speak fluently, to attract tourists, and to convey information to tourists correctly and clearly. Visual delivery of any historical stories, legends, myths is the main feature of the guide. The guide should learn the culture of speech, manners and be able to demonstrate it during the excursion. Because speech culture and manners are the main criteria that determine the general morality of a person. "Speech culture" means conveying the messages that need to be said, respecting the listener, with literary expressions suitable for him.

The concept of "speech" refers to oral and written speech. Both of them will be meaningful, understandable, expressive and modern. Guide's culture of written speech can be seen when working with the following documents: main and individual texts, methodical manuals, abstracts, lectures, reviews, bibliographic images. The main text is written in literary language, and the individual text is written in more spoken language. Speech is divided into external and internal speech. External speech has communicative importance, and its essence is aimed at hearing and understanding of other people. "Establishing contact of a single speaker with many listeners is a relatively complex communicative process". .

Inner speech is the speech of a person's inner world, the pre-formation of thoughts that should be conveyed to the audience. A person has a dialogue with his inner voice thinking about a subject. He thinks with the help of his internal speech, in which he uses auxiliary tools such as drawings, images, tables. When we talk about the public speaking audience, the audience can be complex and very complex. Therefore, when a speaker (guide) goes to a large audience, he must prepare seriously, be ready for any situation and questions. [4]

Guide requirements

The appearance of the guide should include the following:

- compliance with personal hygiene;
- neat appearance;

- discipline in actions;
- cultured dress;
- he should not smoke while working.

In turn, such features leave a warm impression on tourists. It should also have personal qualities. For example,

- good physical health;
- mental stability;
- to be accessible;
- order should be disciplined;
- to be polite;
- should have artistic ability and be able to be a director and organizer. Because the guide is not only a representative of the travel agency, but also his country is a person who advertises his potential, gives new information to the guests and helps them to perform certain actions. The most important thing is that the guide should be able to provide 1st medical aid in case of an accident.

CONCLUSION

Development of the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan, training of all personnel and specialists in this field, welcoming visitors in accordance with all standards and providing them with high-quality services, being able to show the history, culture, traditions of our country accompanied by a guide, and tourists gaining interest is one of the important tasks. Therefore, the field of tour guides serves as an advertiser of the tourist potential of our country and an attractor of tourists.

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BADIIY HUNARMANDCHILIKNING O‘ZIGA XOSILIGI.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7697619>

Tursunova Dildora

Jizzax davlat pedagogika universiteti

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o‘zbek xalqining boy va rang-barang hunarmandchilik an`analari, badiiy hunarmandchilikning o‘ziga xos jihatlari, bugungi kunda jamiyatimizda badiiy hunarmandchilik namunalarini rivojlantirish, badiiy hunarmandchilik mahsulotlarini turli ko`rgazmalarda namoyish etish asosida ularning turlari va sifatini oshirib borish masalalariga e`tibor qaratilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Badiiy hunarmandchilik, xalq hunarmandchiligi, usta-shogird an`analri, hunarmandchilik festivallari, badiiy bezak berish.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассмотрены богатые и красочные ремесленные традиции узбекского народа, уникальные стороны художественных промыслов, развитие образцов художественных промыслов в нашем обществе сегодня, вопросы повышения их видов и качества на основе проявления художественного промысла, продукты на различных выставках, внимание сосредоточено.

Ключевые слова: Художественные промыслы, народные промыслы, традиции мастеров-подмастерьев, ремесленные фестивали, художественное оформление.

Annotation: This article talks about the rich and colorful craft traditions of the Uzbek people, the unique aspects of artistic crafts. Moreover, the article focuses on the issues of development of artistic handicrafts in our society today, increasing their types and quality based on the display of artistic handicraft products at various exhibitions.

Key words: Artistic crafts, folk crafts, master-apprentice traditions, craft festivals, artistic decoration.

Mamlakatimizda bugungi kunda jamiyatning barcha sohalari qatorida madaniyat, sanʼat va xalq hunarmandchiligi sohaslarini yanada rivojlantirishga ham alohida eʼtibor berilmoqda. Respublikamizda maʼnaviy qadriyatlarga hurmat-ehтиrom bilan munosabatda boʻlish, ularni asrab-avaylash va rivojlantirish, milliy hunarmandchilikni, urfodatlarimizni, bebaho tarixiy merosimizni tiklash davlat siyosati darajasiga koʻtarildi. Oʻzbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining “Hunarmandchilikni yanada rivojlantirish va hunarmandlarni har tomonlama qoʻllab-quvvatlash toʻgʻrisida”gi PF-5242 Farmonida ham xalqimizning boy madaniy merosi va tarixiy anʼanalarini toʻliq saqlab qolish va koʻpaytirish, milliy hunarmandchilik, xalq badiiy va amaliy sanʼatini yanada rivojlantirish, hunarmandchilik faoliyati bilan shugʻullanuvchi fuqarolarni har tomonlama qoʻllab-quvvatlash boʻyicha maqsadli va kompleks chora-tadbirlarni amalga oshirish, shu asosda aholi, ayniqsa, yoshlar, ayollar bandligini taʼminlash maqsadida hunarmandchilik sohasida bajarilishi lozim boʻlgan bir qator vazifalar belgilab berilgan.

Xalq hunarmandchiligi naqqoshlik, ganchkorlik, zargarlik, yogʻoch oʻymakorligi, metal oʻymakorligi, kashtachilik, quroqchilik, zardoʻzlik, gilamchilik, gazlama toʻqish, konchilik, pazandachilik, yogʻochlarni kuydirib ishlash, kulolchilik, kosibchilik, mahsidoʻzlik, sangtaroshlik, temirchilik, pichoqchilik, anjomsozlik kabi sohalarga ega boʻlib, oʻzida mehnat va kasb taʼlimining koʻpgina xususiyatlari – amaliyligi, ijodiyliги, milliyliги, mahalliy xom ashyolarni topish va taʼmirlashning qulayliги, oʻgʻil va qiz bolalar mehnatining oʻziga xosliги, murakkab qurilmalar, uskunalar, asboblar va dastgohlar talab qilmasliги, mashgʻulotlarni tashkil etishning soddaligi bilan ajralib turadi.⁸

⁸ Sh. L. Mamasoliyeva. Xalq hunarmandchiligi. Oʻquv qoʻllanma. – Samarqand: SamDU nashri. 2021.

Xalq hunarmandchiligida ma`lum bir hunar turlari ham borli, ular ijodkordan yuksak baddiy mahorat talab qiladi. Ana shunday hunar turlaridan naqqoshlik, ganchkorlik, yog`och o`ymakorligi, kashtachilikdir.

Naqqoshlik — amaliy san`atning qadimiy turi, naqsh yaratish kasbi. Naqqosh usta qog`ozga yoki matoga naqsh mujassamotini yoki naqsh taqsimini chizib oladi (ayniqsa, girih va islmiy kabi murakkab naqshlarda), andoza tayyorlaydi. Amaliy san`at ustalari 2 xil usulda bezak yaratadilar: naqqoshlar tayyorlagan andoza yordamida hamda naqsh (gul) to`g`ridan-to`g`ri bezash jarayoni-da ustalar tasavvurining mahsuli sifatida yaratiladi. Naqqoshlikda naqsh, bezakni malakali naqqosh ustalar chizib beradilar, bunday naqshlarni me`morlik, gilamchilik, kashtado`zlik, kandakorlik va boshqa buyumlardagi naqsh mujassamotlarida birday uchratish mumkin. Naqsh yaratish ustadan did, mahoratdan tashqari qunt, uzoq mashq-malaka talab qiladi. Naqqoshlar o`tmishda xalq ustalarining eng bilim-don, iste`dodli qismini tashkil etgan, ular ustodlarda ta`lim olgan, turli fanlar (adabiyot, musiqa, tarix, kimyo, matematika)ni yaxshi bilgan. Naqqoshlik xalq-amaliy bezak san`atning bir turi sifatida qadimdan o`zbek madaniyatining muhim bo`lagi hisoblanadi. Ko`p asrlar mobaynida uning badiiy an`analari vujudga keldi va rivojlandi.⁹

Ganchkorlik – qadimiy san`at turlaridan bo`lib, o`z aksini dunyo me`morchiligida, jumladan, O`rta Osiyo, Eron, Turkiya va boshqa ko`plab davlatlarda namoyon etib kelmoqda. Ganchkorlik san`ati O`zbekiston me`morchiligi solnomasida muhim o`rin tutib kelgan. Ko`hna tarix yodgorliklari bo`lmish osori atiqalarni kuzatar ekanmiz, o`ymakorlik san`ati oddiy paxsa devorlardan boshlanib, keyinroq ganchkoriy bezaklarga o`tganini ko`ramiz. Hozirgi kunda ganch serquyosh O`zbekistonimizda ardoqlanib va muhofaza qilinayotgan ko`pgina yodgorlik obidalariga ko`rkamlik, go`zallik baxsh etib turibdi. Pardoz

⁹ H. Hudoyberdiyeva. O`zbekistonda naqqoshlik san`ati va yetakchi naqqoshlar tarixi va rivojlanishi . 2021.

turlaridan chok pardoz, pax pardoz, lo‘la pardoz, shabaqa pardozlar keng qo‘llaniladi. Naqsh mujassamotini an‘anaviy o‘simliksimon (islmiy) va handasiy (girix) naqshlar tashkil etadi. Ganch o‘ymakorligi jamoat binolari, turar joylarni bezatishda keng qo‘llaniladi. Jumladan taxmon, tokcha, javonlar o‘yma naqshlar bilan, ularniig yuqori devor bilan shift tutashgan joylari sharafalar bilan bezatiladi, atroflari ensiz zanjira bilan o‘raladi. Badiiy hunarmandchilikning o‘ziga xos an‘analari aks ettiradi.

Yog‘och o‘ymakorligi — badiiy hunarmandlikning qadamiy va keng tarqalgan sohasi. Yog‘ochni kesib, o‘yib, chizib, zaminni teshib naqsh, bo‘rtma shakllar hosil qilib, yog‘och taxtacha va bo‘laklarini birbiriga ulab, yopishtirib handasiy shakllar, o‘simliksimon tasvirlar, islmiy naqshlar hosil qilinadi. Us t a naqshni bezatiladigan sirtga andoza vositasida tushiradi, ustidan naqsh chiziqlari chizib chiqiladi, so‘ng asbob (iskana)lar yordamida o‘yiladi. O‘yishda turli usullar (pargari, bag‘dodi) keng qo‘llaniladi. Yog‘och o‘ymakorligi ko‘p mehnat talab qiladigan soha, unda O‘zbekistonda o‘sadigan mahalliy daraxtlar (qayrag‘och, archa, yongoq, tut, o‘rik, chinor, tol, terak va b.)dan foydalaniladi. O‘ymakor ustalar daraxt yog‘ochlarining xususiyatlarini yaxshi bilishgan (daraxt yog‘ochlarining quyosh nuri ko‘p tushgan tomoni pishiq, zich tolali bo‘ladi). Yog‘ochlar 6 oydan 1 yilgacha suv (hovuzlar)da saqlanadi, soyada quritiladi. Naqsh mujassamotida girih, islmiy naqshlar keng ishlatiladi, mustaqil ravishda girih kamdan kam hollarda qo‘llaniladi; girih va islmiy naqshlar uyg‘unlashtirilib, rangbarang jozibali mujassamotlar, namoyonlar yaratiladi. Bezak (naqshlar) yaratishda pargardan ko‘proq foydalanilishi tufayli naqshlar pargari deb ataladi.

Bezak san‘ati — san‘at turi, inson atrofidagi moddiy muhitni shakllantiradi, badiiy bezash uchun xizmat qiladi, unga estetik va g‘oyaviy badiiy mazmun baxsh etadi. Bezak san‘ati insonning xizmatidagi buyumlarga bezak bo‘lib, shu bilan bir qatorda insonga estetik, g‘oyaviy va badiiy ta‘sir ko‘rsatadi, inson moddiy muhitining kurki, nafosati sifatida namoyon bo‘ladi. Asosiy sohalari: me‘morlik bilan bevosita bog‘liq bo‘lgan monumental bezak san‘ati, jamoatchilik va ayrim

shaxslar ehtiyoji uchun badiiy buyumlar tayyorlash bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan amaliy san‘at, bayram, tomosha manzaralarini, sayrgohlarni, ekspozitsiyalarni, ko‘pchilik e‘tiboriga havola qilinadigan stend, vitrinalarni bezash bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan bezash san‘ati, badiiy loyihalashdan iborat bo‘lgan.

Kashtachilik — [kashta](#) tikish kasbi, amaliy san‘atning qad. sohalaridan biri. Arxeologik topilmalar Kashtado‘zlikning deyarli barcha xalqlarda qad.ligini, iqlim, tabiiy sharoit, muhit bilan bog‘liq holda har bir xalqning madaniyati, san‘ati, kasb-hunar turlari bilan birga, ularning ta‘sirida rivoj topganini ko‘rsatadi. Kashtado‘zlikning paydo bo‘lishi teridan qilingan kiyimlarda bog‘lam va choklarning yuzaga kelishi bilan bog‘liq. Davrlar davomida toshdan suyak bigizlarga, undan metall bigizlarga o‘tish b-n, shuningdek, to‘qish, mato to‘qish, bo‘yash va b. ishlar bilan bog‘liq. Kashtado‘zlik taraqqiyotini Qad. Osiyo, Yevropa, Amerika madaniy yodgorliklari, adabiy manbalardagi kashtalar tasvirida, shuningdek, saqlanib qolgan Kashtado‘zlik namunalarida kuzatish mumkin.

Kashtachilik - O‘zbekiston amaliy bezak san‘ati turlari orasida o‘zining qadimiy an‘analariga ega bo‘lgan san‘at turi hisoblanib, O‘rta Osiyoning yirik savdo hunarmandchilik markazlari va qishloqlarida keng tarqalgan.¹⁰

Bugungi kunda mamlakatimizda badiiy hunarmandchilikni rivojlantirish usta hunarmandlarimiz tomonidan yaratilgan buyumlarni keng ommaga namoyish etish borasida ham islohatlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Respublikamizda o‘tkazilayotgan Xalqaro Hunarmandchilik festivali ham buning taqqol isbotidir.

Butunjahon hunarmandlar festivali har ikki yilda bir marta Qo‘qon shahrida o‘tkazilishi milliy hunarmandchilik va turizmni rivojlantirishda qutlug‘ qadam bo‘ldi. Keyingi yillarda an‘anaviy ko‘rinish olishi kutilayotgan festival jahon

¹⁰ F. To‘xtamisheva. Qashqadaryo vohasi an‘anaviy kashtado‘zligining rivojlanish xususiyatlari 07.00.07 – etnografiya, etnologiya va antropologiya tarix fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) dissertatsiyasi Termiz 2022

miqyosida turistlarni eng ko‘p jalb etadigan xalqaro anjumanlardan biriga aylanishini ta’minlaydi. Festival kunlari tarixiy ziyoratgohlar bo‘ylab uyushtiriladigan sayyohatlar, hunarmandchilik va milliy liboslar ko‘rgazmalari, badiiy va hujjatli filmlar tomoshalari, kitoblar, albom va fotosuratlar savdolari, askiya va qiziqchilar, folklor va dorbozlik jamoalari, polvonlar chiqishlari xalqimizning asrlar mobaynida sayqallanib kelayotgan qadriyatlarni butun dunyoga tarannum etadi.

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1. Sh. L. Mamasoliyeva. Xalq hunarmandchiligi. O‘quv qo‘llanma. – Samarqand: SamDU nashri. 2021.
2. H. Hudoyberdiyeva. O‘zbekistonda naqqoshlik san’ati va yetakchi naqqoshlar tarixi va rivojlanishi . 2021.
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4. Qo‘qon — Butunjahon hunarmandlar festivali mezboni. Xalq so‘zi// 2022.

PUNKTUATSION BELGILARNING MATNDA QO`LLASH QOIDALARI VA ME`YORIY ASOSLARI

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G'aniyeva Xayriniso Baxtiyarovna

Jizzax davlat pedagogika universiteti

Maktabgacha va boshlang'ich ta'limda xorijiy til kafedrasini mudiri. dotsent

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada tilshunoslikning muhim bo`gini bo`lmish punktuatsiya yo`nalishining o`ziga xosligi, matnda qo`llanilishi hamda me`yoriy asoslari muhokama etiladi.

Kalit so`zlar: punktuatsiya, me`yor, qoida, tilshunoslik, tinish belgisi.

KIRISH

Tilshunoslik fani tilda bo`layotgan barcha o`zgarishlarni atroflicha o`rganadi. Tilshunoslik tarixining eng muhim sahifalari borasida tasavvur hosil qilish, barcha lisoniy ta`limotlar, yo`nalishlar haqida fikr bildirish, til va jamiyat, til va tafakkur, til va madaniyatning o`zaro munosabatlarini uzoq yillar davomida o`rganish va tahlil qilish natijasida tilshunoslik, adabiyotshunoslik, tarjimashunoslik, terminologiya, psixologiya, falsafa kabi fanlarning yangidan-yangi qirralari va turlarining rivojlanishiga asos bo`lmoqda.

Har bir fanning o`z tarixi, o`z madaniyati, o`z taraqqiyot yo`li mavjud. Bu borada tilshunoslik fani ham xoli emas. Har bir tilshunos o`z ixtisosligi tarixini, madaniyatini, muammolarini hamda dolzarb masalalarini bilmog`i lozim.

ASOSIY QISM

Tinish belgilari – muayyan tilda yozma nutqni to`g`ri, ifodali, mantiqli bayon qilishda, uni ixchamlashtirishda, gap bo`laklarining o`zaro mantiqiy – grammatik munosabatlarini ko`rsatish uchun xizmat qiladigan grafik vositalar hisoblanadi. Ularning asosiy vazifasi nutqning mazmuniy bo`linishini ko`rsatish, shuningdek, uning sintaktik tuzilishi va intonatsion jihatini aniqlashga yordam berishdir.

B.N.Golovin ta'kidlashicha: "Til me'yori – bu til birliklari va uning qurilishini o'zaro yaxshi tushunish zarurati tufayli paydo bo'lgan, undan foydalanuvchi xalq tomonidan yaratilgan amaldagi qoidalar yig'indisidir".

Punktuatsiya lotincha so'z bo'lib, "nuqta", "joy" ma'nolarini anglatadi. Punktuatsiya tinish belgilarining qo'llanilishi haqidagi bo'limdir. Tinish belgilari me'yori – punktuatsion me'yor yozma nutqqa xos bo'lib, tinish belgilari o'z o'rnida ishlatilmasa, gapning mazmuni hamda sintaktik tuzilishi o'zgaradi. Punktuatsiya asosi deganda, tinish belgilarining qo'llanishi nimaga bog'liqligi tushuniladi.

Punktuatsiya, bir tomondan yozuvchiga o'z yozma nutqini to'g'ri va aniq ifodali bayon eta olish imkoniyatini beradi, ikkinchi tomondan esa, o'quvchiga muayyan matndagi fikrni yozuvchi bayon etganidek, yozuvchining maqsadiga muvofiq tushuna olish imkoniyatini yaratadi.

O'zbek tili punktuatsiyasining birinchi asosi o'zbek tilining grammatik sistemasinutqning mazmun, intonatsiya va tuzilish tomonlarining bir butunligini tashkil qiladi.

Tilshunoslikda punktuatsiya atamasi uch xil ma'noda qo'llaniladi:

- 1) tinish belgilari sistemasi va ularning qo'llanish qoidalari haqidagi bilim;
- 2) tinish belgilarining qo'llanishi haqidagi qoidalar to'plami;
- 3) tinish belgilari.

Qo'llanish o'rniga ko'ra, tinish belgilari uch guruhga bo'linadi:

- 1) Gap oxirida qo'llanadigan tinish belgilari
- 2) Gap o'rtasida qo'llanadigan tinish belgilari
- 3) Aralash qo'llaniladigan tinish belgilari.

Ifodalanmoqchi bo'lgan mazmun tugallangan bo'lsa, nuqta, undov yoki so'roq belgisi, ko'pnuqta qo'yiladi. Masalan:

- Men maktabgacha ta'lim markazi ochmoqchiman... .
- Ta'lim markazi?
- Ta'lim markazi!
- Akam innovatsion markazi ochmoqchi... .

- Innovatsion markaz?
- Innovatsion markaz!

Tinish belgilari gap va nutqning mazmun mundarijasini shakllantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydigan fonetik-fonologik vositalarni (ko'tariluvchi ohang, pasayuvchi ohang, sanash ohangi, to'lqinli ohang, pauza kabi supersegment birliklarni) yozuvda ifodalash uchun ko'rsatiladi.

Hozirgi o'zbek yozuvida tinish belgilari qo'yidagilarni tashkil qiladi: nuqta, ikki nuqta, ko'p nuqta, vergul, nuqtali vergul, so'roq belgisi, tire, undov belgisi, qavs, qo'shtir- noq. Mazkur tinish belgilari XIX asrning ikkinchi yarmida ayrim gazeta va toshbosma kitoblarning nashr etilishi bilan paydo bo'lgan.

Nuqta – eng qadimgi va eng ko'p qo'llanuvchi tinish belgilaridan biri. Nuqta gapoxirida qo'llaniladi. Uning qo'llanishi logik-grammatik prinsipga asoslanadi. Bunda stilistik yoki differensiya prinsiplariga asoslanadi.⁷¹

Vergulning ishlatilish o'rinlari turlicha bo'lib, gapning uyushiq bo'laklarini ajratish uchun, juft uyushiq bo'laklardan so'ng, zidlovchi bog'lovchilardan oldin, erkalash, xursandlik, achinish ma'nosini anglatuvchi -ye, -ey, -yey yuklamasidan keyin, kirish so'z, kirish ibora, kirish gaplar, takror gaplar va takror bo'laklar va ko'plab holatlarda vergul qo'llaniladi.

Qavsning o'zbek yozuvda tinish belgisi sifatida qo'llanishi XIX asrning 70-yillari-dan boshlangan.

So'z, so'z birikmasi yoki ayrim gapga izoh berish maqsadida ishlatiladigan qurilmalar qavs ichiga olinadi. Kiritma so'z, kiritma birikma, kiritma gaplar qavs qo'yiladi. Parcha yoki misol uchun tanlangan gaplarga doir manba ma'lumotlari qavsga olinadi.

Undov belgisi ham undov gaplar, ham buyruq gaplar oxiriga qo'yiladi. Undov belgisihis-tuyg'uga ega bo'lgan gaplar oxiriga, his-hayajon bilan aytiladigan undalma, buyruq gaplarda qo'yiladi. Fikrga to'liq e'tiroz bildirish, qo'shilmaslik, taajjub, shubhasini bildirish maqsadida qavs ichida undov belgisi ishlatiladi.

XULOSA VA MUNOZARA

Xulosa qilib aytganda, yozma matndagi har bir tinish belgi muayyan sintaktik- stilistik hodisani aks ettiradi, shuningdek ular yozma nutqdagi maqsadni aniq ifodalash uchun qo'llaniladi. Bugungi kunda hayotimizda tinish belgilarida foydalanishning xizmati ortib, uning vazifasi va qo'llanish doirasi kengayib bormoqda. Bu esa, matbuot va nashriyot ishlarining yanada keng rivojlanishi, o'zbek yozuv madaniyatining tobora taraqqiy etishi, adabiy til ta'sirining kengayishi, nutq madaniyatining keng ko'lamda ravnaq topishi va o'sishi, kitobxonlikning tubdan takomillashuviga olib kelmoqda.

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ТАРЖИМОН ФАОЛИЯТИДА МАДАНИЯТНИНГ ЛИСОНИЙ ВОҚЕАЛАНИШИ

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Рузиева Махфуза Хикматовна,

Бухоро давлат университети таянч докторанти

ruzieva.mahfuza@gmail.com

Аннотация: Тилни воқеликнинг ажралмас қисми сифатида тан олиш маданиятга нисбатан самарали таржима фаолиятини амалга ошириш учун пойдевор сифатида муносабатда бўлишни тақозо этади. Ҳозирги вақтда таржимон нафақат икки тил тизимини ўзига хос семантик код сифатида эгаллаши, балки шунингдек уларнинг ўз мавжуд маданий маконида ҳаракат қилиши лозимлиги ҳақидаги фикр ўз тасдиғини топмоқда.

Калит сўзлар: маданият, когнитив фаолият, лисоний тафаккур, этноментал тажриба.

Маданиятга хос муаммони ҳал қилишдаги ёндашув кўп жihatдан тилшуносликдаги энг асосий муаммо – нутқ ва тафаккур, тил ва фикр нутқининг ўзаро мутаносиблиги ва шу билан бирга таржима учун энг биринчи даражали масала ҳисобланган универсаллик ва идиоэтникликнинг ўзаро мувофқлиги ҳамда кейингисининг узатилиш имкониятлари ва усулларининг талқин қилинишига боғлиқ. Таржима амалиёти шуни кўрсатадики, ушбу жараёнда юзага келадиган мушкулликлар “асл” лингвистик хусусиятга эга бўлибгина қолмай, нафақат лисоний мувофқликликларнинг йўқлиги, балки ундан ҳам муҳимроқ, *этноментал тажрибадаги*, хусусан, мулоқотчиларнинг нутқий хулқ-атворидаги тафовутга ҳам боғлиқдир.

Тарихий-график маълумотларга мурожаат қилиш таржимада маданий ўзига хосликнинг табиати, таржимоннинг вазифалари, бу орқали юзага келган муқаррар ўзгаришлар ва бунинг натижасида унинг фаолиятига ўсиб бораётган қизиқиш, асл матни она тилига ўгиришда механик кўчиришдан то тақдим этилган маълумотнинг

вербализацияси содир бўладиган ақлий жараёнларни аниқлашга уринишгача бўлган қарашлар ўзгаришини кўриш иконини беради.

Таржима фаолиятининг жозибadorлиги, кўпроқ, унинг ёрдамида тадқиқотчини бир тил тарафидан чизилган доирадан чиқиб, бошқа бир тил “руҳининг ҳиссий таассуротлари ва беихтиёр ҳаракатлари тўпламидан” [Гумболдт 1964, 93-бет] тўқилган доирага қадам босиш мумкинлигини англашга яқинлаштира олиши мумкинлиги билан белгиланади.

Гумболдтнинг тил ҳақидаги “Инсон ва унга ички ва ташқи жиҳатдан таъсир кўрсатадиган табиат ўртасида жойлашган” макон сифатидаги тасавури, бир тил тарафидан чизилган доирадан чиқиб, бошқа бир тил “руҳининг ҳиссий таассуротлари ва беихтиёр ҳаракатлари тўпламидан” [Гумболдт 1964, 93-бет] тўқилган доирага қадам босиш мумкин эканлигини ифода этади.

Гумбольдтнинг тилни “Инсон ва унга ички ва ташқи жиҳатдан таъсир кўрсатадиган табиат ўртасида жойлашган” макон [Гумболдт 1964, 99-бет], ҳамда коммуникация амалга ошириладиган “борлик”, муҳит сифатидаги тасавури тил ва таржимада маданиятшуносликка оид йўналишни бошлаб берди.

“Тил назариясида оламнинг лисоний манзараси (тил манзараси) тушунчасининг пайдо бўлиши, тил ва тафаккурнинг ўхшаш эмаслиги ва шунга мувофиқ, барча тиллар учун бир хил ва умумий бўлган фикр мазмунидан истисно тарзда тил мазмунига тегишли томонининг мантиқий маълумотларини рад этиш фикрлашга оид мазмун билан бир қаторда алоҳида тил мазмунини ҳам ажратиб кўрсатишни англатади” [Зубкова 1998, 206-207 б.].

Таржима амалиётида тилларнинг ўзига хослиги ҳақидаги интуитив, эндигина шакллантирилган фикр, алоҳида нозик фарқларни бир тилдан иккинчи тилга механик тарзда қайта ифодалашга уринишларнинг бефойдалиги ҳам кузатилади.

Бу “сўз – маъно”, “сўзма-сўз - эркин таржима” дихотомиясида ёрқин намоён бўлиб, бир неча асрлар мобайнида янги вазифаларга ечим излашни тақозо этадиган баҳс-мунозараларни келтириб чиқардики, бу ечимлар аниқ шакллантирилган таълимотлар кўринишига эга бўлмаган ҳамда алоҳида назариялар сифатида шакллантирилмаган бўлсада, замонавий таржима назарияларининг асосини ташкил эта олди. Аста-секин таржима амалиёти жараёнида ҳар даврининг адабий-эстетик ва сиёсий қонунлари ҳақида фикр юритиш мобайнида эркин таржима етакчи ўринни эгаллади.

Тил Худога тегишли ва Худо тил орқали таржимани текшириши, назорат қилиши ва Инжил таржимасининг бенуқсон бўлиши ҳақида ғамхўрлик қилиши. Биринчиси билан бевосита боғлиқ бўлган иккинчи момент - бир тилда баён қилинган нарса, иккинчи тилда баён қилиниши мумкин деган ишончга олиб келувчи *идиоэтникликни эътиборга олмасликдир*.

Бир неча асрлар ўтиши билан, универсализм ўзининг мустаснолик мавқеини йўқотади. Уйғониш даврида икки матн ўртасидаги мазмунгаий ва бадий номувофиқлик ҳолатлари таржимонларни *таржима қилиниши имкониятидан таржимоннинг энг муҳими, асл нусханинг ўзига хослиги ва жозибадорлигини илғаб олишдек потенциал қобилятидан ва энг асосийси асл нусханинг ўзига хослиги ва жозибасини етказа олишидан шубҳаланишга мажбур қиларди*. Бугун Сервантеснинг XVII асрда янграган машҳур таққослаши ўзининг тарафдорларига эга: “.....таржима <...> – бу ичкараси ташқарига қилинган фламанд гилами билан баробардир; шакллар кўриниб туради, бироқ ишларнинг сероблиги уларни камроқ равшан қилади ҳамда олд томондаги каби у қадар силлиқлик ва кўзимизни камаштирадиган бўёқлар йўқ”. [Федоров 1983, 26-бет].

Биз А.В. Федоровнинг мазкур сўзлардан энг аввало англанадиган бадий матннинг (ифодаланган кузатиш ҳар қандай матн учун хос бўлиб, унинг функционал-услубий мансублигига боғлиқ эмас деб ҳисобланади) лисоний ўзига хос хусусиятга эгаллиги ва маълум бир тил билан узвий боғлиқлиги ҳақидаги фикрига қўшиламыз. “Ўз даври учун бундай хулоса, шубҳасиз, тилшунослик

тафаккури тараққиётида олға қадамни англатиши, ҳам танқидий, ҳам ўзига хос тарзда прогрессив ҳисобланган бўлар эди, зеро бу *бир хил фикрларни айнан ўта ўхшаш усулларда ифодалаш* каби *турли тиллар ҳақидаги содда тасаввурдан воз кечилини* англатади” [Федоров 1983, 26].

Жумладан, *биринчи* йўналиш тарафдорлари тилда шакл ва мазмун ўртасидаги боғлиқлик тасодифий, тил грамматикаси мантиқий ва универсал деб эълон қилишган ва барча тиллар бир моҳиятнинг намоёни деб ҳисоблашган. *Психологик* йўналиш тарафдорлари эса, аксинча, шакл ва мазмун бирлигига эътибор бериб, шакл мазмунга қўшимча маъно олиб киришга қодир, ва бу, демак, ҳар бир алоҳида тилнинг ўзига хослигини олдиндан белгилаб беради, деб ҳисоблашган.

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FRANSUZ ADABIYOTIDA MASAL JANRINING SHAKLLANISHI, TABIATI VA JANRIY BELGILARI

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Xorijiy tillar kafedrasi katta o'qituvchisi

Nosirova Dilfuza Mustafoyevna.

Xorijiy tillar fakulteti talabasi **Baxshulayeva Parvina**

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada masal janrining tabiati va janriy belgilari haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit soʻzlar: milliy tarix, tadqiqot, badiiy asar, anʼana, masalchilik, doston

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается природа жанра притчи и жанровые особенности

Ключевые слова: Национальная история исследование художественное произведение традиция притча эпос.

Annotatsiya: This article discusses the nature of the parable genre and genre features.

Keywords: National history, research, artistic work, tradition, parable, epic

Tarixga nazar tashlasak, jahon adabiyotining sermahsul qirralari, shuningdek fransuz adabiy merosining ilk yodgorliklari IX asrning ikkinchi yarmiga toʻgʻri keladi. Bu soʻf diniy mazmundagi asarlar edi. Lekin X asrga kelib lotin adabiyoti bilan tanishgan sayyor qoʻshiqchilar, shoirlar tufayli "janglyorlar poeziyasi" paydo boʻladi. "Janglyorlar" birinchi epik dostonlar – jestlarni, yaʼni, "faoliyat qoʻshiqlari"ni yaratishdi. Ular syujetining asosida VIII - X asr boshlaridagi tarixiy voqealar, chunonchi, sarkarda Buyuk Karl xalqlarining koʻchish davri voqealari yotadi. Asta-sekin bu asarlarning syujetiga biror-bir voqea-hodisaning bayoni bosh maqsad etib qoʻyila borib, keyinchalik biror bir qahramon, buyuk bir shaxs haqida kuylanadigan hamda ular alohida toʻplamlarga yigʻila boshlangan. Buyuk Karl nomi bilan bogʻliq toʻplamlar ancha mashhur boʻlgan. Shunday toʻplamlardan mashhur fransuz qahramonlik eposining yodgorligi "Rolland haqida qoʻshiq" hozirgi

kunlargacha mashhurdir. Bu asar syujetiga yurtini bosqinchilardan saqlab qolish uchun o`zini qurbon qilgan qahramon haqida bayon qilinadi. "Roland haqida qo`shiq" jahon xalqlarining bolalarga bag'ishlangan dastlabki mashhur fransuz adabiyoti namunasidir.

XVIII asr Fransiyada adabiy ertaklar an`anaviyligi sifatida e`tirofga sazovor. Bu aslida bolalarga emas, kattalarga mo`ljallangan adabiyot sifatida yuzaga kelgan. Ungacha ham bolalar adabiyoti degan alohida tushuncha mavjud bo`lmay, faqat keyingi asrdagina bolalar kitobxonligi hodisasi voqelikka aylangan. Ya`ni, kattalar adabiyotidan qayta ishlanib, kichkintoylar uchun soddalashtirilgan, ularga moslashtirilgan adabiyot paydo bo`ldi. Shunday nashrlarga Fransua Rablening XVI asrda yozilgan va Uyg'onish davri adabiyotining yorqin namunasi sifatida o`rin olgan "Gargantuya va Pantagryuel" asaridir. Butun Evropada bo`lgani singari Fransiyada ham bu davr dunyo va insonni kashf etish, inson qadriyatlarini, uning ijodiy imkoniyatlari va intilishlari davri bo`ldi. Uyg'onish davri yozuvchi va shoirlari o`zlarining ijodlari bilan insoniyat olamining barcha jabhalarini qamrab olishdi. Ming yillar mobaynida madaniy taraqqiyot davomida insoniyat son - sanoqsiz adabiy asarlar yaratdi, ular orasida odamning atrofidagi dunyo haqidagi g'oyalarini aks ettirish shakli va shakliga o'xshash ba'zi asosiy turlarini ajratish mumkin. Bu adabiyotning uch turi (yoki turi): *doston, drama, matn*. Har bir adabiyot turining farqi nimada?

Shunday bo`lsa-da, adabiyotda hali ertak va masallarga nisbatan past nazar bilan qarash illati mavjud edi. Go`yoki, "ertakona" an`ana faqatgina jiddiy bo`lmagan, "badiiy jihatdan zaif adabiyot"dagina uchragan. Ammo Rable o`zining mashhur romanida hech ikkilanmay, folklordagi ulkan odamlar (velikanlarning) obrazidan foydalandi. Fransiyada romantizm bilan birga xalq ijodi va madaniyatiga yetuk estetik hodisa sifatida qiziqib murojaat qilish, Yevropaning boshqa mamlakatlaridan ancha keyin shakllandi. Bilamizki, xalq ertaklarini yig'ib yozish esa XIX asrning yetmishinchi yillaridagina boshlandi. XVII asr oxiri Sharl' Perro ertaklarining yaratilishi bilan belgilanadi va uning ertaklari fransuz adabiy

ertaklarining eng zo`r hamda yorqin namunalari sifatida e`tirof etiladi. Fransiyada XVIII asr esa ertaklarning oltin asri hisoblanadi. Uyg'onish davrida talaygina shoir va yozuvchilar bu universal janrga ko`p murojaat qilgan va uning estetik imkoniyatlaridan foydalanib, dolzarb mavzular bilan boyitib borishgan. Masalan, Val'ter falsafiy ertaklar yozgan. Sharqning "Ming bir kecha" ertaklari fransuz tiliga tarjima qilingach, sharqona ertaklarga o`xshatishlar paydo bo`ldi. Ammo shu XVIII asrning o`zidayoq ertaklarning urf bo`lishi ancha pasaydi. Ilgari bolalarga mo`ljallangan maxsus adabiyot yo`qligi uchun kichkintoylar kattalarning asarlarini o`qishar edi. Keyingi asrlarda esa Sharl' Perroning qisqartirilgan ertaklaridan aynan bolalar uchun namunalar tayyorlangan. Ulardan shafqatsizlik, erkinlik, badiiy o`yinlar olib tashlanib, anchayin soddalashtirilgan. Russoning inson aql-zakovatiga siqinish hamda dunyoga ongli ravishda nazar solishi kabi pedagogik nazariyalari ham Uyg'onish davri bilan bog`liq. Masalchilik haqida fikr yuritmoqchi bo`lsak, quyidagi masalni misol qilib olishimiz mumkin.

Ikki do'st va ayiq

Ikki do'st o'rmonda aylanib yurganlarida to'satdan ayiqqa duch kelib qolishibdi. Ulardan birinchisi shoshib daraxtga chiqib olibdi va ayiqning changalidan qutulib qolibdi.

Ikkinchisi esa, hech narsa qo'ldan kelmasligini bilib, o'zini o'lganga solib yotib olibdi.

Ayiq yerda yotgan kishining oldiga kelib, qulog'ini hidlabdi. Hatto uni turtib ham ko'ribdi. Kishini o'lgan deb o'ylab, unga tegmasdan ketib qolibdi. Ayiq ketgach, haligi kishining do'sti daraxtdan tushib kelib: — Do'stim, ayiq qulog'ingga nima deb shivirladi? — deb so'rabdi. — U menga: qiyinchilik paytida tashlab ketadigan do'st bilan sayohatga chiqishni yaxshilab o'ylab ko'rmabsan-da, dedi, xolos, — deb javob beribdi do'sti.

Qissadan hissa: Do'stlik qiyinchilikda sinaladi. EZOP MASALLARI

Qomusiy olimning ijodiy va falsafiy me`rosiga, xuddi o`sha davr yangi g'oyalarining hamda bolalar ta`lim-tarbiyasining xazinasini sifatida murojaat qilishgan.

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SIGNIFICANCE OF THE FEMOFLOR TEST IN ASSESSING THE STATE OF VAGINAL MICROBIOCENOSIS IN PRETERM VAGINAL DISCHARGE

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G.M. Kayumova, N.K. Dustova

*Department of obstetrics and gynecology Bukhara state medical institute
named after Abu Ali ibn Sina*

Annation. Among the problems of modern obstetrics and pediatrics, premature birth occupies one of the main places. But premature discharge of the amniotic fluid is one of the main reasons for premature labor. Amniotic fluid plays an important role in the biomechanics of childbirth and is of great physiological importance for the state of the fetus, because the amniotic fluid creates conditions for the free development and movement of the fetus, and also protects the developing fetus from negative effects.

Key words: Premature discharge of amniotic fluid, premature babies, preterm birth, genital tract biocenosis, vaginal microbiocenosis.

The purpose of the study is to determine the qualitative and quantitative composition of microorganisms that make up the microbiocenosis of the genital tract in pregnant women with premature discharge using PCR.

Research materials and methods. Vaginal swabs of 28 pregnant women who came to the perinatal center of Bukhara region before the period of 26-34 weeks and 24-36 years of age were studied. The control group consisted of 11 pregnant women aged 24-36 with a physiologically developing pregnancy of 20-25 weeks. We used the Femoflor-16 test to study the biocenosis of the urogenital tract in women. Quantitative evaluation of vaginal microflora was carried out both in absolute and relative terms. The absolute indicator is the amount of DNA of the desired microorganism in the sample, expressed in GE, expressed as a decimal logarithm - lg. The relative quantitative indicator of the microorganism was

calculated as the ratio of the amount of the desired microorganism to the amount of the total bacterial mass. It is presented in two formats: the decimal log difference of the number of the respective group of microorganisms and the total bacterial mass and as a percentage of the total bacterial mass.

Research results. Normocenosis was found in 10 cases of women with premature amniocentesis. Among them, only 1 patient was diagnosed with absolute normocytosis, and in the rest, 8 out of 9 cases had conditional normocytosis with fungi of the genus *Ureaplasma (urealyticum + parvum)* and *Candida spp.* In 1 case, the titer was more than 10⁴ and 10³, respectively. Anaerobic dysbiosis was detected on average in 7 (25%) women with premature amniotic fluid. 24-70% of the total bacterial mass in cervical smears of patients was *Lactobacillus spp.* organisms. *Eubacterium spp.* It was detected in high titers in 2 pregnant women. A combination of anaerobic bacteria and microorganisms associated with bacterial vaginosis was found in 5 cases. Normocenosis was found in 10 out of 11 cases (90.9%) in physiologically developing women of pregnancy. Of them, absolute normocenosis was observed in 4 women, conditional normocenosis in 6 women. Among women with conditional normocenosis, *Ureaplasma (urealyticum + parvum)* was detected in 4 cases, fungi belonging to the *Candida* genus were detected in 1 patient, and both pathogens were detected in diagnostic titers in 1 pregnant woman. Severe anaerobic dysbiosis with a physiologically developing pregnancy from 11 pregnant women It was found in 1. The etiological structure is represented by the following pathogens: *Gardnerella vaginalis/Prevotella bivia/Porp Streptococcus spp.*, *Gardnerella hyromonas spp.*, *Eubacterium spp.*, *Atopobium vaginae*, *Ureaplasma (urealyticum+parvum)*.

Summary. In women with physiological pregnancy, lactobacilli decreased by only 9.1% (p=0.002), in most cases normocytosis was detected. Anaerobic microorganisms (14 out of 28 or 50%) played the main role in the structure of dysbiosis in pregnant women with premature amniocentesis: *Gardnerella vaginalis* (17.8%), *Candida spp. genus fungi* (10.7%), *Ureaplasma (urealyticum + parvum)* -

17.8%, *Atopobium vaginae* (7.1%). *Aerobic dysbiosis* was noted only in 2 women (7.1%), *Streptococcus spp.* and *Candida spp. fungi* of the genus, mixed - observed in 2 (7.1%) cases. The identified facts confirm the point of view about the important role of bacterial vaginosis in the genesis of premature birth, emphasize the need to diagnose dysbiosis in the restoration of normal microflora.

O‘ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDA XIZMAT XATLARINING USLUBIY XUSUSIYATLARI

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Kosimova Mukammal Umaraliyevna

Farg‘ona davlat universiteti

Ingliz tili o‘qitish metodikasi kafedrasida o‘qituvchisi

Annotatsiya Xizmat yozishmalari kundalik hujjatlarning muhim qismiga aylangan bo‘lib, ularni har qaysi sohada uchratishimiz mumkin. Barcha tillarda ushbu turdagi hujjatlarning mavjudligi ularning umumiy va farqli xususiyatlarini tadqiq etishni talab etadi. Ushbu maqola o‘zbek va ingliz tillarida xizmat yozishmalarining qiyosiy tahliliga bag‘ishlangan kata bir tadqiqotning kichik bo‘lagi bo‘lib, unda asosan ingliz va o‘zbek tillarida rasmiy xatlarning uslubi va formati tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so‘zlar: rasmiy uslub, xizmat xatlari, aniqlik, rasmiy xatlar

Abstract Business correspondence has become an important part of daily documents, and we can meet them in any field. The existence of documents of this type in all languages requires the study of their common and different features. This article is a small part of a larger study devoted to the comparative analysis of business correspondence in Uzbek and English languages and it mainly analyzes the style and format of official letters in English and Uzbek languages.

Key words: official style, business letters, formal letters, concreteness

Kirish

Ish yuritish jarayoni turli hujjatlardan iborat bo‘lib, tadqiqotchilar tomonidan ularning turlanishi ham har xildir. Boshqa uslublar kabi rasmiy uslub ham o‘z maqsadiga ega bo‘lib, hujjatlarning asosiy vazifasi ikki tomon o‘rtasidagi shartlarni bayon qilishdir. Ikki tomon deganda tashkilot-tashkilot, davlat – fuqaro, davlat-davlat, tashkilot-hodim o‘rtasidagi munosabatlar tushuniladi. Hujjatlar uslubi umumiy xususiyatlarga ega bo‘lishiga qaramay, yuqoridagi har bir tur o‘z

xususiyatiga, maxsus soʻzlariga, oʻziga xos formatiga ega hisoblanadi. Barcha turdagi hujjatlarni tahlil qiladigan boʻlsak, ular orasida eng keng tarqalgani xatlardir. Rasmiy xatlarni biznes hujjatlari orasida ham, diplomatik yozishmalar ichida ham uchratishimiz mumkin. Ingliz tilida ular alohida rasmiy xatlar (formal letters) tarzida oʻrganilsada, ular ham bir necha turlarga boʻlinadi. Masalan, tashkilotlar oʻrtasidagi, tashkilot va klient oʻrtasidagi munosabatlarni izga solib turuvchi hujjatlar ham asosan xatlar boʻlib, ular biznes xatlar deb ham ataladi. Oʻzbek tilida xizmat yozishmalari deb yuritiluvchi taklif xat, iltimos xat, axborot xat, tasdiq xati va boshqalar ingliz tilida ish yozishmalari (business correspondence) deb ataladi. Xizmat yozishmalarining asosiy maqsadi tashkilotlar oʻrtasida, tashkilot ichida, hodimlar oʻrtasida rasmiy ravishda axborot almashishdir. Ikki tomon oʻrtasida almashinayotgan axborotning rasmiyligini xatlar yoki xizmat yozishmalari taʼminlab beradi. Ushbu yozishmalar yoki xatlarning ish yuritish jarayonida yoki biznes jarayonlarini amalga oshirishda oʻrni beqiyos boʻlib, tomonlar oʻrtasidagi mavhumlikni aniqlashtirish, maʼlum maqsadda takliflar berish, soʻrash uchun juda qulaydir.

Asosiy qism

Ingliz va oʻzbek tillarida xatlar keng tarqalgan boʻlsada, ular uslubiy jihatdan bir-biriga oʻxshash va farqli jihatlarga egadir. Umumiy jihatdan qaralganda ikki tilda ham xatlar qisqa va xolisligi asosiy talab hisoblanadi. Xatlar ish jarayonining bir boʻlagi hisoblangani sababli ham, ularning qisqa, tushunarli aniq boʻlishi ish yuritish jarayonining samarali boʻlishini taʼminlaydi. Xizmat yozishmalarining umumiy xususiyatlaridan biri bu matnning qurilishi va xatning formatidir. Barcha rasmiy xatlar odatda maxsus ish qogʻozlariga va turiga qarab qatʼiy formatda yoziladi. Rasmiy yozishma va hujjatlar tili umumiy ravishda boshqa stildagi matnlardan farqlovchi xususiyatlarga egadir. Hujjatlarga qoʻyiladigan asosiy talab bu ularning holisligidir. Yani hujjatlar hamma uchun bir hilda tushunarli boʻlishi, har bir oʻquvchi tomonidan turli maʼnolar anglashilmasligi lozim. Shuning uchun hujjatlar tilida juda ham koʻp cheklovlar uchraydi. Hujjatlarni yaratishda avvalo

tilning adabiy me'yorlariga to'liq rioya qilish lozim. Shu bilan birgalikda, ularning tili aniq, ixcham, lo'nda va mazmunan to'liq bo'lishi talab etiladi. Kichraytirish-erkalatish qo'shimchali so'zlar, shevaga oid so'zlar, tantanavor ruhdagi jumlar, obrazli nutq vositalari va jargonlar hujjat matnida noholislikka olib kelishi sababli ular hujjatlarda qo'llanilmaydi.

Xizmat yozishmalarining eng ko'zga ko'rinadigan tarafi ifoda uslubining standard ekanligidir. Yani, fikrlar berishda, ifoda qilishda ikki tilda ham ma'lum bir standartlarga, qoliplarga asoslanadi. Misol uchun, o'zbek tilida taklif xati doimo "Muhtaram(a)" yoki "Hurmatli" so'zi bilan boshlansa, ingliz tilida esa barcha turdagi xatlar Dear Sir/Madam kabi so'zlar bilan boshlanadi.

O'zbek tilidagi xatlar mazmun jihatdan uch qismdan iborat bo'lib, birinchi qism xat bilan murojat qilish uchun sababni ifodalaydi. Ikkinchi qism ushbu masala qay darajada muhim ekanligi tushuntirib beradi. Uchinchi qism esa xat yozishdan asosiy maqsadni ko'rsatib beradi. Ushbu qismlar xatning formatida aniq ajratib ko'rsatilmasa ham mazmunan xat matnida seziladi.

Ingliz tilida esa rasmiy xatlar salomlashish, asosiy qism, shuningdek, niyat, istak yoki minnatdorchilikni o'z ichiga oluvchi so'nggi qismdan iborat. Ingliz tilida barcha rasmiy xatlarda xatning boshida xatni qabul qiluvchi aniq ko'rsatiladi: Dear Mr/ Mrs/ Miss/. Ms Brown kabi. Xat jo'natilayotgan shaxs jo'natuvchi uchun notanish bo'lsa, unda Hurmatli janob/honim (Dear Sir/Madam) so'zlaridan foydalangan holda murojaat qilasiz. Yoki xat qabul qiluvchining ish joyidagi unvoni yoziladi: Dear Human Resources Professional (Hurmatli inson resurslari bo'yicha mutaxassis), Dear sales Manager (Hurmatli sotuv menejeri), Dear Sales Team (Hurmatli savdo-sotiq jamoasi), Dear Members of Selection Committee (Hurmatli tanlov komissiyasi a'zolari) kabi. Ma'lumotnoma yoki tavsiyanoma yozilayotganda esa huddi o'zbek tilida ba'zi hujjatlarda "So'ralgan joyga", "tegishli shaxsga" deb yozilgani kabi "To whom it may concern" birikmasi ishlatiladi. Xatlarni shakllantirishda sarlavha yozish majburiy bo'lmasada, ingliz tilida ham sarlavha kiritish tavsiya etiladi. chunki, xatni qabul qiluvchida xatni to'liq o'qimasidan avval

u haqida qisqa tushuncha paydo bo‘ladi. Trkibi jihatdan xatlarning asosiy qismi uch qismga bo‘linadi. Birinchi qism xatning maqsadini ifodalasa, ikkinchi qism xat yozish uchun sabablarni izohlaydi, uchinchi qism xatni oluvchidan nima kutilayotgani aniq yoziladi. Xatlarning turiga qarab bu qismlar biroz farqli ravishda berilsada, lekin ingliz tilidagi barcha xatlar maqsadni ifodalashdan boshlanadi.

Rasmiy xatlarga qo‘yiladigan asosiy talablardan biri bu uning qisqa va ayni paytda to‘liq va mufassalligidir. Matnning hajm jihatdan qisqaligi uning mazmuniga putur yetkazmasligi, mazmuni to‘g‘ri tushunishga to‘sqinlik qilmasligi lozim. Odatda rasmiy yozishmalar 1 betdan 3-4 betgacha bo‘lishi mumkin. Iltimos xat, so‘rov xati, kafolat xati eslatma xat, farmoyish xat va eslatma xatlari hajmi juda qisqa bo‘lib, odatda 1-3 gap orqali mazmun ifodalanadi. Ilova xat, axborot xati, talabnoma va da’vo xatlarining hajmi odatda bir betdan ko‘p bo‘lishini vaziyatni keng va batafsil muhokama qilish deb izohlash mumkin.

Xulosa

Ramiy-idoraviy uslub yoki ish yuritish uslubining asosiy bo‘g‘ini hisoblangan xizmat yozishmalar (business correspondence) uslubiy jihatdan nafaqat boshqa uslublardan balki boshqa hujjat turlaridan ham farqlanib turar ekan. Ular ish jarayoni faol ishlatilishi bilan birga ikkita aniq tomonlar o‘rtasidagi munosabatni ifodalashga xizmat qiladi. Shuning uchun ham matnlarning ikkinchi bir tomonga qaratilganligini, shuningdek ikki tomon o‘rtasida tushunmovchiliklar bo‘lmasligi uchun qisqa va aniq bo‘lishini xatlarning matni va mazmunidan anglash mumkin.

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O‘ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDA XIZMAT XATLARI

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Kosimova Mukammal Umaraliyevna

Farg‘ona davlat universiteti

Ingliz tili o‘qitish metodikasi kafedrasida o‘qituvchisi

Annotatsiya Rasmiy yozishma va hujjatlar tili umumiy ravishda boshqa stildagi matnlardan farqlovchi xususiyatlarga egadir. Ular mazmun jihatdan turfa hil, foydalanish doirasi jihatidan qamrovi ham juda kengdir. Xizmat hujjatlari tashkilotning turli masalalariga oid bo‘lib ularning asosini xatlar tashkil etadi. Bular asosan, so‘rov xati, iltimos xat, da‘vo xati, kafolat xati, tasdiq xat, farmoyish xat kabilar bo‘lib kim tomonidan yozilishi jihatdan ham bir biridan farqlidir. Ushbu maqola o‘zbek va ingliz tillarida xizmat xatlarining umumiy va farqli xususiyatlari haqida ma‘lumot beradi va tahlil qiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: rasmiy uslub, xizmat yozishmalari, xizmat xatlari, so‘rov xati

Abstract : The language of official correspondence and documents generally has characteristics that distinguish it from other styles of text. They are diverse in terms of content and very wide in terms of scope of use. Service documents relate to various issues of the organization. These are basically a request letter, a claim letter, a guarantee letter, a confirmation letter, an order letter, etc. This article provides information and analyzes the common and different features of service letters in Uzbek and English.

Key words: officialize, business correspondence, service correspondence, a letter of enquiry

Kirish

Mamlakatimizning har tomonlama, ham siyosiy, ham iqtisodiy tarafdin rivojlaib borayotgani nafaqat ichki, balki tashqi savdoning ham yuksalishiga sabab bo‘lmoqda. Biznes muloqotlari hoh og‘zaki, hoh yozma tarzda amalga oshirilsin, o‘ziga xosligi bilan ajralib turadi. Mijozlar yoki biznes hamkorlar bilan yuzma-yuz

muloqot bilan birga yozma muloqot ham muhim o‘rin egallaydi. Ish va biznes bo‘yicha olib boriladigan yozma muloqot vositalarining hammasi ish, xizmat yoki biznes yozishmalari (ingliz tilida business correspondence) deb ataladi. Xizmat yozishmalari odatda rasmiy xatlardan iborat bo‘lib, bir tashkilotning boshqasi bilan, mijoz bilan o‘zaro kelishuv va axborot almashuvlarini o‘zida aks ettiradi. Xatlar ham shaxsiy, ham xizmat yozishmalarining asosi hisoblanadi. Xatlar xizmati kerak bo‘lmaydigan hech bir soha yoki ish mavjud emas. Xatlar biznes muloqot, diplomatik aloqalarning muhim bo‘lagi. Xizmat yozishmalarining eng ko‘zga ko‘rinadigan tarafi ifoda uslubining standard ekanligidir. Yani, fikrlar berishda, ifoda qilishda ikki tilda ham ma’lum bir standartlarga, qoliplarga asoslanadi. Misol uchun, o‘zbek tilida taklif xati doimo “Muhtaram(a)” yoki “Hurmatli”so‘zi bilan boshlanadi. Ingliz tilida esa barcha turdagi xatlar Dear Sir/Madam kabi so‘zlar bilan boshlanib, xatning birinchi gapidayoq xatni yozishdan maqsad bayon etiladi.

Asosiy qism

Xatlarda ishlatilayotgan so‘zlardan ular qaysi turga oid ekanligini sezish qiyin emas. Bu ayniqsa ingliz tilida yaqqol ko‘zga tashlanadi. Odatda ingliz tilida barcha xizmat yozishmalari rasmiy xatlar sifatida qabul qilinadi. Masalan a letter of request (letter of enquiry)-iltimos xati, order letter-buyurtma xati, letter of complaint-shikoyat xati kabilar. Avvalo, xatlarning formati xaqida to‘htaladigan bo‘lsak, ingliz tilida rasmiy xatlarning barchasi quyidagi formatda yoziladi va yozuv chap tomonga teriladi:

1. Xat jo‘natuvchining manzili
2. Sana
3. Xatni qabul qilib oluvchining manzili
4. Xatning mavzusi (masalan, Subject: order of furniture- mebel buyurtmasi)
5. Salomlashish
6. Xatning asosiy qismi
7. Xotima (iltifotli so‘zlar bilan xatni yakunlash)
8. Imzo

O‘zbek tilida xizmat xatlari ikki turga yani javob talab qiluchi va javob talab qilmaydigan guruhdagi xatlarga bo‘linadi. Lekin ularning turli guruhga mansub bo‘lishi shakliga deyarli ta’sir ko‘rsatmaydi. Barcha xatlar bir hil qolipda yoziladi.

Xizmat xatlari quyidagi zaruriy qismlami o‘z ichiga oladi¹¹:

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi gerbi.
2. Muassasaning ramziy belgi (emblema)si.
3. Mukofotlar.
4. Vazirlik, boshqarma nomi.
5. Tashkilot nomi.
6. Bo‘linma nomi.
7. Tasniflagich bo‘yicha hujjatning xos raqami.
8. Muassasaning xos raqami.
9. Pochta, telegraf manzili, bankdagi hisobraqami.
10. Sana.
11. Shartli raqam.
12. Kelgan hujjat shartli raqami.
13. Hujjatning kelish sanasi.
14. Hujjat jo‘natiladigan manzil (xatni oluvchi muassasaning nomi).
15. Munosabat belgisi (rezolyutsiya).
16. Nazorat haqida belgi.
17. Matn sarlavhasi (xatning qisqacha mazmuni).
18. Matn.
19. Ilovalar haqida belgi.
20. Imzo.
21. Rozilik belgisi (viza).
22. Kelishuv haqida belgi.
23. Bajaruvchi haqida belgi va uning telefon raqami.

¹¹ Davlat tilida ish yuritish. Amaliy qo‘llanma. Aminov M va boshqalar.2020. 351-352 bet

24. Bajartilganlik haqida belgi.

Xatlarning nomi har doim ham yozilmaydi, lekin xat nima haqida ekanligi sarlavha tarzida bayon etiladi. Masalan, “Universitet oshxonasini ta’mir qilish uchun qo‘shimcha mablag‘ ajratish haqida”, “Kafolat berish haqida”. Sarlavha mazmunan qanchalik aniq bo‘lsa, ish yuritish jarayonida shunchalik yaxshi samara va qulaylik bo‘lishini ta’minlaydi.

Xizmat xatlarining barchasi ham mazmun jihatdan uch qismdan iborat bo‘ladi. Birinchi qism xat bilan murojat qilishning asosiy sababini o‘z ichiga olsa, ikkinchi qism bu masala qay darajada muhim ekanligi dalillar keltirish orqali isbotlab beriladi. Uchinchi qism esa xat yozishdan asosiy maqsadni ifodalaydi. Ushbu qismlar xatning formatida ko‘zga tashlanmasligi ham mumkin, lekin mazmunan xat matnida seziladi.

Ingliz tilida rasmiy xatlar salomlashish, asosiy qism, shuningdek, niyat, istak yoki minnatdorchilikni o‘z ichiga oluvchi so‘nggi qismdan iborat. Xatlarning asosiy qismi uch qismdan iborat bo‘lib, birinchi qism xat yozishdan maqsadni ifodalasa, ikkinchi qism bunga sabablarni izohlaydi, uchinchi qism xatni oluvchidan nima kutilayotgani aniq yoziladi. Bu albatta xatlarning turiga qarab bir-biridan farqlanishi mumkin, lekin ingliz tilidagi barcha xatlar maqsadni ifodalashdan boshlanadi. Yoki sabab va maqsad birinchi gapdayoq ko‘rsatiladi. Yani xatni o‘qishni boshlaganingizdayoq ushbu yozishmaning asosiy mazmunidan xabardor bo‘lasiz.

Xulosa

Nafaqat ingliz yoki o‘zbek tilida balki barcha tillarda ham xatlar rasmiy muloqotning asosiy vositalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Texnologiyalar rivojlanib o‘zaro shaxsiy yozishmalar ijtimoiy tarmoqlar orqali amalga oshirilayotganiga qaramay, rasmiy munosabatlarni ifodalashda xatlar o‘z o‘rnini yo‘qotmagan. Qolaversa, emaillar orqali jo‘natiladigan rasmiy xatlar ham o‘zaro xizmat muloqotining muhim bir bo‘g‘ini hisoblanadi.

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